

A Compendium to S-Phase Entry and Exit

Andrew Burgess^{1,2,8*}, Jenny Vuong^{3,4,8}, Kamila A. Marzec¹, Ulrik Nicolai de Lichtenberg⁵, Seán O'Donoghue^{3,4,5} and Lars Juhl Jensen^{7*}

¹ ANZAC Research Institute, Sydney NSW 2010, Australia

² The University of Sydney Concord Clinical School, Faculty of Medicine and Health, Sydney, NSW, Australia

³ Garvan Institute of Medical Research, Sydney NSW 2010, Australia

⁴ Data61, CSIRO, Eveleigh NSW 2015, Australia

⁵ School of Biotechnology and Biomolecular Sciences, University of New South Wales, Kensington NSW 2052, Australia

⁶ Novo Nordisk Foundation, Tuborg Havnevej 19, Hellerup 2900, Denmark

⁷ NNF Center for Protein Research, University of Copenhagen, 2200 Copenhagen N., Denmark

⁸ *These authors contributed equally*

*Corresponding authors: andrew.burgess@sydney.edu.au and lars.juhl.jensen@cpr.ku.dk

Introduction

S-phase entry and exit is regulated by many protein complexes that assemble 'just-in-time', orchestrated by thousands of distinct events - including external signals, subcellular translocation, phosphorylation, association, transcription, and degradation (Jensen et al., 2006). To help understand how these complex processes regulate S-phase, we selected 83 events believed to play key roles, and used them to create a tailored visualization (Burgess et al., 2019) based on the 'Minardo' layout, in which time flows around a schematic 'cirtanglar' cell (Ma et al., 2013).

In an interactive version of this visualization – available at <https://minardo.org/s-phase> – clicking on each event opens a popup with a text summary, and with links to supporting literature in PubMed, protein sequence information in UniProt (The UniProt Consortium, 2019), and related 3D structures in Aquaria (O'Donoghue et al., 2015). Below, in this publication, we have compiled this information from the 83 popups in the online interactive visualization, thereby making this information more easily accessible, and to also better acknowledging the contributions of the >280 scientific publications used in assembling the visualization.

We designed the S-phase visualization to complement our earlier visualization on the phosphoregulation of mitosis (Burgess et al., 2017; <https://minardo.org/mitosis>). Both can be displayed together, giving a comprehensive overview of the events regulating the mitotic cell cycle.

1. Late G1 – Growth Factor Stimulation and preparation of S-Phase

1.1. ERK Kinase Signalling

The RAS–RAF–MEK–ERK signal cascade (or ERK for short), is a part of the mitogen-activated protein kinase (MAPK) pathway and plays a central role in linking extracellular mitogenic stimuli with intracellular signalling cascades that drive cell cycle progression during G1 phase. This pathway

is heavily disrupted in multiple cancer types highlighting its importance to cell homeostasis (Liu et al., 2018).

1.2. Multisite phosphorylation on ERK

Growth factors bind to receptor tyrosine kinases, triggering a cascade of signalling within the cell via the Ras–Raf–MEK–ERK pathway (reviewed in (Katz, Amit & Yarden, 2007; McCubrey et al., 2007)). Other growth factor signalling pathways can also promote cell proliferation, including PI3K/AKT (Liang & Slingerland, 2003), Hedgehog (Duman-Scheel et al., 2002), and Wnt/Beta-catenin pathways (Niehrs & Acebron, 2012). Notably, receptor tyrosine kinases are commonly mutated, amplified and overexpressed in cancer, resulting in uncontrolled and premature cell cycle entry (Porter & Vaillancourt, 1998; Fleuren et al., 2016).

1.3. CDK4/6

Cyclin-dependent kinase 4 and 6 (CDK4 and CDK6) bind to D-type cyclins and are important for G1/S cell cycle progression. They initiate the phosphorylation of the retinoblastoma transcriptional corepressor (RB1), with hypo-phosphorylated RB1 binding to and blocking E2F gene transcription during G1 phase (Fisher et al., 2016).

1.4. p16 – CDK4/6

p16, encoded by the CDKN2A gene, binds to CDK4 and CDK6, preventing Cyclin D binding and formation of active Cyclin D – CDK4/6 complexes during G1 phase, thereby preventing downstream phosphorylation of RB1 and G1/S progression (Serrano, Hannon & Beach, 1993; Coleman et al., 1997).

1.5. MYC transcription factor family

The MYC family (MYC, MYCN, MYCL) of transcription factors are proto-oncogenes that drive expression of a vast number of genes, including Cyclin D1 (CCND1) in response to mitogenic signalling (Dang et al., 2012).

1.6. Phosphorylation of MYC on S-62 by MAPK

Phosphorylation of MYC (and MYCN) on S-62 by MAPK promotes MYC stability and accumulation, thereby increasing transcription of MYC target genes such as Cyclin D1 (Sears et al., 2000). CDK5 has also been implicated in S-62 phosphorylation (Seo et al., 2008).

1.7. Cyclin D expression

The MYC family, along with Mad – Max transcription factors work to regulate the transcription of multiple genes, including the Cyclin D proteins (CCND1-3), which are essential for G1/S progression (Grandori et al., 2000; Dang et al., 2006; Dong et al., 2014).

1.8. p16 inhibition of CDK4/6

p16 (CDKN2A) and related INK family members, such as p18, bind to CDK4/6 distorting the Cyclin binding domain on the kinase, thereby reducing the affinity of Cyclin D for

CDK4/6 (Russo et al., 1998; Jeffrey, Tong & Pavletich, 2000).

1.9. Cyclin D binding to CDK4/6

Cyclin D competes with p16 (CDKN2A) for binding to CDK4. Consequently, increased expression of Cyclin D is thought to titrate p16 away from CDK4/6, allowing nuclear import and subsequent activation of Cyclin D – CDK4/6 complexes (Coleman et al., 1997).

1.10. p21/p27 binding to CDK4/6

p27, which is encoded by the CDKN1A gene, binds to and stabilizes active Cyclin D – CDK4/6 complexes in the nucleus (Cheng et al., 1999; Bagui et al., 2003). p27 binding appears to promote subsequent activation of Cyclin D – CDK4 by mitogenic signalling (Ou et al., 2011).

1.11. Multisite phosphorylation of p27

Multisite phosphorylation of p27 is required to permit subsequent CAK (CDK7, Cyclin H, Mat1) phosphorylation of CDK4. Multiple kinases and tyrosine (Y) phosphorylation sites have been implicated in p27 phosphorylation, including Brk kinase and phosphorylation of Y-88 (Bockstaele et al., 2006; Ray et al., 2009; Patel et al., 2015). Phosphorylation of p27 by AKT on T-157 and T-198 has been shown to precede and appears to promote p27 – Cyclin D – CDK4 complex formation (Larrea et al., 2008). Finally, phosphorylation of p27 on T-187 by CDK2 promotes its subsequent SCF–Skp2-dependent degradation during G1/S phase (Das et al., 2016). Efficient phosphorylation of T-187 requires prior phosphorylation of Y-88 and Y-74 by the Src family of kinases (Chu et al., 2007; Grimmmer et al., 2007). Destruction of p27 during G1/S is dependent on its nuclear accumulation (Swanson, Ross & Jackson, 2000) and recruitment of p27 – CyclinE – CDK2 complexes by the origin-recognition complex (ORC), CDC6 and MCM Pre-IC components (Furstenthal et al., 2001).

1.12. Phosphorylation of CDK4/6 on T-172 by CAK

CAK (CDK7, Cyclin H, Mat1) is proposed to phosphorylate CDK4/6 kinase on its T-loop at T-172 (T-177 in CDK6), thereby promoting activation of CDK4 kinase (Schachter et al., 2013), possibly via an indirect mechanism involving p21/27 phosphorylation (Bisteau et al., 2013). JNK kinase has also been implicated in the phosphorylation of T-172 on CDK4 (but not CDK6) that is in complex with Cyclin D1 and p21 (Colleoni et al., 2017).

1.13. The Retinoblastoma Protein (RB1)

During G1 phase, the retinoblastoma protein (RB1) is bound to DP – E2F1-3 complexes that are assembled on DNA, and represses transcription of E2F promoters, thereby preventing cell cycle progression and entry into S phase (Takahashi, Rayman & Dynlacht, 2000 and reviewed in Bertoli, Skotheim & de Bruin, 2013). Repression of Cyclin E is also achieved through ORC1 binding to RB1 and through the histone methyltransferase SUV39H1, which

work to repress E2F1 mediated transcription of Cyclin E (Hossain & Stillman, 2016).

1.14. JNK kinase family

c-Jun N-terminal kinases (JNK) are members of the MAPK family and primarily respond to stress (Zeke et al., 2016), however recent evidence suggest that they may also function to activate Cyclin D/CDK4 complexes during G1/S (Colleoni et al., 2017).

1.15. Multisite Phosphorylation of p21 by JNK

The stability of the Cyclin-dependent kinase inhibitor p21 (Waf1/Kip1) is regulated by multisite phosphorylation. The JNK, p38 and ERK1/2 family of kinases have been implicated in phosphorylation of p21 on T-57 and S-130, resulting in stabilization of p21 – Cyclin D – CDK4 complexes (Kim et al., 2002; Bisteau et al., 2013), indicating that JNKs function as activating kinases for p21 bound Cyclin D – CDK4 complexes (Colleoni et al., 2017). This likely creates a positive feedback loop with Cyclin E – CDK2, which also phosphorylates free p21 on S-130 creating a phosphodegredon that promotes SCF–Skp2-dependent degradation of p21 (Bornstein et al., 2003). Similarly, phosphorylation of S-130 during G2/M by CDK1 has also been linked with reduced CDK1 inhibition and destabilization of p21 (Kreis et al., 2016).

1.16. RB1 multisite phosphorylation by Cyclin D – CDK4/6

Unphosphorylated RB1 is bound to and represses DP – E2F1-3 mediated transcription at E2F promoters during G1. The mono-phosphorylation of RB1 by Cyclin D – CDK4/6 complexes during G1 promotes the partial release of RB1 from DP – E2F1-3 allowing transcription of Cyclin E and other G1/S genes. This phosphorylation is linked with controlling the length of G1 phase (Dong et al., 2018). Mono-phosphorylation of S-807/S-811 likely primes RB1 for further phosphorylation on other sites. Notably, 14 independent isoforms of mono-phosphorylated RB1 have been identified in G1 (Narasimha et al., 2014).

2. The Restriction Point

2.1. Expression of Cyclin E

E2F1 strongly promotes the transcription of Cyclin E (CCNE1-2) during G1/S. The rise in Cyclin E levels promotes the subsequent formation of Cyclin E – CDK2 complexes, which drives progression through the restriction point (R). This commits the cell to entering S phase and completion of the cell cycle (DeGregori, Kowalik & Nevins, 1995; Ohtani, DeGregori & Nevins, 1995). RB1 is bound to and represses DP – E2F1-3 mediated transcription at E2F promoters during late G1. Repression of Cyclin E is also achieved through ORC1 binding to RB1 and the histone methyltransferase SUV39H1, which work to repress E2F1 mediated transcription of Cyclin E (Hossain & Stillman, 2016).

2.2. Cyclin E binding to CDK2

Cyclin E forms a complex with CDK2 during late G1 phase (Honda et al., 2005). This complex is then responsible for hyper-phosphorylating RB1, which in turn promotes the transcription of more Cyclin E, thereby creating a positive amplification loop that drives cells through the restriction point (R), and commits cells to completing the cell cycle (reviewed in (Fisher, 2016)). CCNE2 (Cyclin E2), is also expressed and can bind to, and form active CDK2 complexes during G1/S (Lauper et al., 1998; Zariwala, Liu & Xiong, 1998).

2.3. Dissociation of p21/p27 from CDK2 complexes

Dissociation and destruction of both p21 and p27 help to promote CDK activity required for passage through the Restriction point (R) in late G1 (reviewed in (Bachs et al., 2018)). Specifically, p21 degradation during G1/S correlates with passage through the Restriction Point (R) in daughter cells that have lower levels of CDK2 activity (Moser et al., 2018). Destruction of p27 during G1/S is dependent on its nuclear accumulation (Swanson, Ross & Jackson, 2000) and recruitment of p27 – Cyclin E – CDK2 complexes by the origin-recognition complex (ORC), CDC6 and MCM Pre-IC components (Furstenthal et al., 2001).

2.4. Phosphorylation of CDK2 on Y-15 by WEE1

WEE1 kinase phosphorylates CDK2 on Y-15 thereby inhibiting Cyclin E – CDK2 activity (Gu, Rosenblatt & Morgan, 1992; Watanabe, Broome & Hunter, 1995; Welburn et al., 2007). Failure to phosphorylate CDK2 results in premature S-phase entry, rapid Cyclin E degradation, abnormal DNA replication, and genome instability in cells (Hughes et al., 2013).

2.5. Phosphorylation of CDK2 on T-160 by CAK

CDK-activating kinase (CAK), which in humans is likely the trimeric CDK7 – Cyclin H – Mat1 complex (Tassan et al., 1995), phosphorylates CDK2 kinase on its T-loop at T-160, which is required for full kinase activity (Brown et al., 1999). This phosphorylation can potentially be made by ERK1/2, CDK20 and by CDK2 itself (Lents et al., 2002; Liu, Wu & Galaktionov, 2004; Abbas et al., 2007; An et al., 2010).

2.6. Dephosphorylation of CDK2 on Y-15 by CDC25A

CDC25A is a dual-specificity phosphatase that removes the inhibitory Y-15 and T-14 phosphorylations on CDK2/1, which are made by the WEE1 and MYT1 kinases (Gu, Rosenblatt & Morgan, 1992; Mazars et al., 2009). The removal of these phosphorylations from CDK2 promotes a positive feedback loop during the Restriction point (R), where CDK2 hyper-phosphorylates RB1 leading to increased expression of Cyclin E, increasing the pool of active Cyclin E – CDK2 complexes. Notably, phosphorylation of CDC25A by CDK4 during G1 promotes its ubiquitination and degradation, creating a negative feedback-loop that prevents premature entry into S-phase (Dozier et al., 2017). Several additional phosphorylation sites (including S-76, S-80, S-82, S-88, S-279 and S-293) on

CDC25A also promote its degradation in response to DNA damage during G1 and S phase (Sørensen et al., 2003; Kang et al., 2008).

2.7. Hyperphosphorylation of RB1

Hyperphosphorylation of RB1 reduces its affinity for binding to E2F1-3 thereby diminishing its transcriptional repressive activity (reviewed in (Rubin, 2013)). The Cyclin E – CDK2 complex is responsible for hyper-phosphorylating RB1, which prevents it from binding to and suppressing E2F1-3 mediated transcription. This in turn promotes the transcription of more Cyclin E, creating an amplification loop that amplifies CDK2 activity (Moser et al., 2018). Notably, cells appear to require a defined and precise threshold of CDK2 activity to enter and commit to S-phase (Schwarz et al., 2018). The activation of this Cyclin E – CDK2 amplification loop is likely the mechanism controlling the restriction point (R), which is the point at which cells no longer require mitogens and become committed to completion of the cell cycle (reviewed in (Fisher, 2016)).

2.8. E2F1-3 driven transcriptional of G1/S genes

The E2F1-3 family of transcription factors drive the expression of genes required for G1/S progression, including ORC, CDC6, MCM2-7, CDT1 and NPAT ((Grant et al., 2013; Fischer et al., 2016) and reviewed in (Fischer & Müller, 2017)). CDC6 plays a critical role in establishing the Pre-Replication complex (Pre-RC) during G1. CDC6 binds to the origin recognition complex (ORC), where it then recruits the MCM2-7 hexamer bound to CDT1 (Yuan et al., 2017).

3. The Pre-Replication Complex

3.1. Pre-Replication Complex (Pre-RC)

After the loading of the first MCM2-7 hexamer, a second MCM2-7 hexamer is loaded by CDT1, forming a double hexamer (Remus et al., 2009; Evrin et al., 2009), which is necessary to enable extensive unwinding of DNA origins (Champasa et al., 2019). This forms a core DNA helicase consisting of ORC, CDC6, and two copies of MCM2-7, known as the Pre-RC (Pre-Replication Complex), which is later phosphorylated and activated by DDK promoting DNA strand unwinding. For more details see (Sun et al., 2014).

3.2. The origin recognition complex (ORC)

The origin recognition complex (ORC) consists of 6 family members (ORC1-6), which assemble at replication origins during early G1 phase and initiate the formation of the pre-replication complex (Pre-RC) (Li and Stillman, 2012).

3.3. CDC6 binding

The assembly of the Pre-Replication Complex (Pre-RC) involves the stepwise recruitment of ORC1-6, CDC6, CDT1, and MCM2-7, of which the latter are organised in a hexameric complex (Fernández-Cid et al., 2013; Yeeles et al., 2015). The first step requires the recruitment of ORC

proteins to replication origins. During late S phase and through mitosis, ORC proteins are heavily phosphorylated by CDKs, preventing their binding to origins of replication. This ensures that newly synthesized DNA is not re-licensed during S-phase and that only one round of DNA replication occurs. During early G₁, ORC proteins are dephosphorylated, possibly by the PP1 phosphatase (Lee et al., 2014), allowing their recruitment to origins. See the following reviews for more details (Pozo & Cook, 2017; Parker, Botchan & Berger, 2017; Moiseeva & Bakkenist, 2018).

3.4. MCM2-7 – CDT1 binding

CDT1 plays an important role in the loading of the MCM2-7 hexamer complex onto DNA. CDT1 interaction with MCM 2, 4 and 6, holds the MCM complex open allowing it to wrap around the DNA (Zhai et al., 2017a; Frigola et al., 2017). The already loaded ORC – CDC6 complex then triggers MCM-dependent ATP hydrolysis (Kang, Warner & Bell, 2014), which triggers the expulsion of CDT1 and closure of the MCM ring complex. For more information on the MCM2-7 complex see (Zhai et al., 2017b).

3.5. Treslin binding and multisite phosphorylation by CDK2

In human cells, Treslin (TICRR) binds TOPBP1 and collaborates with the CDK2-mediated loading of CDC45 and GINS onto replication origins to create the CMG (CDC45 – MCM2-7 – GINS) complex (Kumagai et al., 2010; Boos, Yekezare & Diffley, 2013). CDK2 phosphorylates Treslin at T-969 and S-1001, which regulates the number and timing of replication origin firing (Kumagai et al., 2011; Sansam et al., 2015). CDK2 phosphorylation of Treslin is enhanced by CKS proteins, which are often overexpressed in cancer (Mu et al., 2017). Notably, the MASTL – ENSA – PP2A axis regulates Treslin levels, with loss of ENSA resulting in degradation of Treslin, most likely due to dephosphorylation of CDK sites on Treslin by PP2A. Reduced Treslin leads to a reduction in active origins and a subsequent increase in S-phase transit time (Charrasse et al., 2017). Treslin can also stimulate the phosphorylation of MCM2 by DDK during S phase (Bruck & Kaplan, 2015).

3.6. TOPBP1 binding

TOPBP1 (DNA topoisomerase 2-binding protein 1) is a candidate homologue of budding yeast Dpb11, it works in concert with Treslin to load CDC45 onto the MCM2-7 Pre-RC complex in vertebrates (Kumagai et al., 2010). Its precise role in regulating replication in human cells is not fully understood, however appears to be required for efficient DNA replication and interacts with GINS, promoting its loading onto origins and formation of the CMG complex (Tanaka et al., 2013). In addition, TOPBP1 activates the ATR – ATRIP complex (Kumagai et al., 2006) during DNA replication to ensure that local dormant origins do not fire (Sokka et al., 2018). TOPBP1 also plays several additional roles throughout the cell cycle including regulating DNA repair, ultrafine bridge resolution in

mitosis, transcription and cell cycle checkpoints (Wardlaw, Carr & Oliver, 2014).

3.7. RECQL4 – MCM10 binding

RECQL4 (RECO4) appears to be essential for the efficient initiation of DNA replication in higher eukaryotes (Kliszczak et al., 2015). It binds with MCM10, CDC45 and GINS, with MCM10 binding stabilizing the RECO4 – MCM replicative helicase complex (Xu et al., 2009; Thangavel et al., 2010). Mutations in RECQL4 are associated with several autosomal recessive syndromes that result in premature aging and higher rates of cancer (Mo, Zhao & Balajee, 2018). MCM10 plays important roles in activating helicase activity of the CMG complex (Lööke, Maloney & Bell, 2017), origin melting and recruitment of Pol α (Perez-Arnaiz et al., 2017), and for bypassing blockages encountered during replication by isomerizing the CMG – DNA complex (Langston et al., 2017).

4. Formation of the CMG Complex

4.1. CMG Complex

The CMG (CDC45 – MCM – GINS) helicase complex is responsible for unwinding the DNA double helix and for recruiting the additional enzymes required for DNA replication ((Georgescu et al., 2017; Douglas et al., 2018) and reviewed in (Onesti & MacNeill, 2013; Kang et al., 2018)). Full CMG assembly requires phosphorylation of MCM2-7 by DDK (Abid Ali et al., 2017). In yeast, there is evidence for the Pre-Initiation Complex (Pre-IC), which is an intermediate state in-between the inactive Pre-RC and the active replication fork (Miyazawa Onami, Araki & Tanaka, 2017). The CMG complex also plays an important role in bypassing protein-DNA obstacles encountered during replication (Sparks et al., 2019).

4.2. GINS – CDC45 binding

Activation of the two loaded MCM2-7 hexamers requires binding of CDC45 and the hetero-tetrameric GINS complex, which forms the CMG complex (CDC45 – MCM2-7 – GINS). Formation of a stable CMG complex requires all three components of the CMG complex as well as RECQL4, CTF4/AND1 and MCM10 (Douglas et al., 2018). The two CMG complexes unwind the DNA strands and form the basis for the two replication forks that then travel in opposite directions (reviewed in (Seo & Kang, 2018; Li & O'Donnell, 2018)).

4.3. Pol ϵ binding

DNA polymerase epsilon (Pol ϵ) contains four-subunit and is the major leading strand polymerase in eukaryotes. In yeast, Pol ϵ plays important roles converting the inactive MCM hexamers into active helicases, by forming a pre-loading complex (pre-LC) with GINS (reviewed in (Zegerman, 2013)). Pol ϵ binding to the pre-LC complex occurs on the leading strand and is stabilized by DPB2. Pol ϵ also plays important roles in maintaining epigenetic information by ensuring correct histone deposition during replication (Petryk et al., 2018; Yu et al., 2018; Bellelli et

al., 2018a), and pausing of replication forks during stress (Hizume et al., 2018) Notably, disruption of the Pol ϵ complex causes replication stress and cancer (Bellelli et al., 2018b).

4.4. MCM2-7 multisite phosphorylation

MCM2-7 is phosphorylated by Dbf4-dependent protein kinase (DDK). Specifically, DDK phosphorylates the N-terminal tails of MCM2/4/6 ((Bruck & Kaplan, 2009; Sheu & Stillman, 2010) and reviewed in (Larasati & Duncker, 2017)). These phosphorylations are required for the subsequent formation of an active CMG (CDC45 – MCM2-7 – GINS) complex, which is necessary for DNA replication (Deegan, Yeeles & Diffley, 2016; Abid Ali et al., 2017). Claspin recruits DDK, thereby promoting phosphorylation of MCM proteins and triggering DNA replication (Yang et al., 2016). These phosphorylations are removed by protein phosphatase 1 (PP1), which is targeted to DNA by Rif1 (Hiraga et al., 2014; Davé et al., 2014; Alver et al., 2017).

5. Centrosome Duplication

5.1. PLK4 - master regulator of centrosome duplication

Polo like kinase-4 (PLK4), plays an essential role in ensuring that centrosome duplication occurs only once per cell cycle and is linked to the DNA replication cycle during S-phase (Arquint and Nigg., 2016).

5.2. PLK4 autophosphorylation

Homodimeric PLK4 performs trans autophosphorylation on S-293 and T-297 that targets PLK4 for degradation by SCF – β TrCP, thereby limiting its kinase activity and preventing unscheduled centriole duplication. This ensures that centriole duplication is temporally linked to the DNA replication cycle (Cunha-Ferreira et al., 2013; Klebba et al., 2015). This negative feedback loop is important for maintaining a homeostatic clock for centriole growth and size, ensuring that centrioles grow to the correct size and then stop (Aydogan et al., 2018).

5.3. STIL binding to PLK4

The binding of STIL to PLK4 protects it from degradation and promotes activation by enhancing PLK4 autophosphorylation of its activation T-Loop. This creates a positive feedback loop that increases PLK4 concentration and activity. Efficient binding of STIL with PLK4 is promoted by CEP85 and is dependent on coiled-coil regions within STIL (Moyer et al., 2015; Arquint et al., 2015; Liu et al., 2018; Ohta et al., 2018), while USP9X deubiquitinates STIL, preventing its degradation during S-phase (Kodani et al., 2019).

5.4. Multisite phosphorylation of STIL by PLK4

PLK4 phosphorylates STIL on T-33 and S-38 promoting its binding to PLK4 and recruitment to centrioles (Kratz et al., 2015; Dzhindzhev et al., 2017; McLamarrah et al., 2018). PLK4 phosphorylates several additional sites on STIL including multiple serine residues in the STAN motif (e.g. S-1108,S-1116), located on the C-terminal of *Drosophila*

STIL (Ana2), and promotes SAS6 recruitment (Dzhindzhev et al., 2014 and reviewed in (Arquint & Nigg, 2016). CEP152 (Asterless; Asl in *Drosophila*) is also required for loading of PLK4 onto centrioles (Dzhindzhev et al., 2010; Hatch et al., 2010).

5.5. SAS6 recruitment and phosphorylation by PLK4

SAS6 is important for ensuring the correct nine-fold symmetry and cartwheel architecture of centrioles, although this likely requires microtubules as well (Hilbert et al., 2016) and potentially pre-existing centrioles (Wang et al., 2015). Notably, SAS6 is degraded by the E3-ubiquitin ligase SCF – FBXW5, with PLK4 phosphorylation on S-151 of SAS6 blocking ubiquitination (Puklowski et al., 2011).

5.6. ORC1 – CDC6 recruitment to centrosomes

ORC1 and CDC6 are both exported from the nucleus to centrioles during S phase. ORC1 is exported to the cytoplasm, where it is either degraded (Tatsumi et al., 2003) or recruited by Cyclin A to centrosomes (along with MCM5). At centrosomes ORC1 – MCM5 prevents Cyclin E – CDK2 dependent centriole reduplication (Hemerly et al., 2009; Ferguson, Pascreau & Maller, 2010). In addition, CDC6 is also exported from the nucleus and recruited to centrioles by Cyclin A dependent phosphorylation (Petersen et al., 1999; Yim et al., 2013). Here CDC6 acts to restrict centriole over-duplication by binding to SAS6, forming a stable complex with STIL and antagonizing PLK4 dependent centriole duplication (Xu et al., 2017).

5.7. Multisite phosphorylation on CEP135 by PLK4

PLK4 interacts with and phosphorylates CEP135 on potentially nine sites in its N-terminal. This allows CEP135 to correctly position Asterless (*Drosophila*, likely CEP152 in humans), thereby maintaining the correct organization of the centriole (Galletta et al., 2016). CEP135 also interacts with the core centriole protein SAS6 and CPAP providing a linkage to the growing microtubules (Lin et al., 2013; Kraatz et al., 2016).

5.8. CP110 multisite phosphorylation by Cyclin E – CDK2

Cyclin E – CDK2 phosphorylates multiple sites on CP110 during S phase (S-45, S-170, T-194, S-366, S-372, S-400, S-516, and T-566). Disrupting this phosphorylation results in unscheduled centrosome separation leading to multipolar spindles during mitosis (Hu et al., 2015b). Notably, inhibition of CDK2 in lung cancer cells results in anaphase catastrophe, which is reversed upon CP110 overexpression, a common event in cancer (Hu et al., 2015a).

5.9. Phosphorylation of CP110 on S-98 by PLK4

CP110 is an essential centrosomal protein that plays important roles in promoting centrosome duplication and restricting elongation and ciliogenesis (Schmidt et al., 2009). The levels of CP110 are tightly controlled by USP33, which deubiquitinates CP110 preventing SCF-mediated degradation (D'Angiolella et al., 2010; Li et al., 2013). PLK4 phosphorylates CP110 on S-98 during centriole assembly

and likely promotes stabilization of the SAS6 cartwheel, with failure to phosphorylate S-98 inhibiting centriole assembly (Lee et al., 2017).

6. Entry into S-Phase, activation of the helicase and replication of DNA

6.1. Phosphorylation of Cyclin D on T-286 by GSK3

GSK3 phosphorylates Cyclin D1 (CCDN1) on T-286, which promotes association with CRM1 and subsequent export from the nucleus where it is then degraded (Diehl, Zindy & Sherr, 1997; Benzeno et al., 2006). Phosphorylation of T-288 may also be involved in regulating Cyclin D degradation in a DIF-3 dependent manner (Takahashi-Yanaga et al., 2006).

6.2. Degradation of Cyclin D

Cytoplasmic Cyclin D1 can be ubiquitinated by multiple SKP1 – CUL1 – F-box (SCF) E3 ubiquitin ligases (F-Box proteins), including FBXO4, FBXW8, SKP2, and FBXO31, which target Cyclin D1 for proteasomal degradation (Barbash et al., 2009; Vaites et al., 2011; Kanie et al., 2012). Failure to degrade Cyclin D1 is strongly associated with cancer (Knudsen et al., 2006), while recent evidence indicates that the deubiquitylase USP22, which is commonly overexpressed in aggressive cancers, removes ubiquitin from Cyclin D thereby stabilizing the protein and promoting cancer (Gennaro et al., 2018).

6.3. Geminin transcription

Geminin is transcribed during late G1 and early S phase. It binds strongly to CDT1 and prevents its association with the MCM-complex at origins of replication, thereby ensuring that the DNA replication only occurs once per cell cycle (Wohlschlegel et al., 2000; Lee et al., 2004; Lutzmann, Maiorano & Méchali, 2006). Geminin also plays important roles in regulating the centrosome duplication cycle ((Tachibana et al., 2005; Lu et al., 2009) and reviewed in (Arbi et al., 2018)).

6.4. Phosphorylation of CDT1 on T-29 by CDK2

CDT1 is phosphorylated by CDK2 during early S phase on its cyclin-binding motif on T-29 and possibly several other sites. CDK phosphorylation results in the binding of CDT1 to the F-box protein SKP2 leading to the subsequent ubiquitination and degradation of CDT1. Notably, phosphorylation also inhibits CDT1 binding to DNA but does not affect Geminin binding (Liu et al., 2004; Sugimoto et al., 2004; Takeda, Parvin & Dutta, 2005)

6.5. Degradation of CDT1

Removal of CDT1 from DNA and subsequent degradation or binding to Geminin prevents relicensing of origins of replication, thereby preventing re-replication (reviewed in (Pozo & Cook, 2017)).

6.6. Multisite phosphorylation on ORC1 by CDK2

ORC1 is phosphorylated by S-phase CDKs (most likely CDK2 bound to either Cyclin E or A) after the G1/S transition.

This results in its nuclear export, ubiquitination by SCF E3 ligases and subsequent degradation during S phase (Méndez et al., 2002). ORC2 is phosphorylated by CDK2 on T-116 and T-226 in S phase, which dissociates ORC2 from chromatin and replication origins (Lee et al., 2012).

6.7. Topoisomerase and unwinding of the DNA

Topoisomerase (TOP1 and TOP2) functions to relieve the wide variety of DNA supercoils that are generated in front of the replication fork during DNA replication (reviewed in (Branzei & Foiani, 2010; Vos et al., 2011)).

6.8. Multisite phosphorylation on MCM2-7 by CDK2

CDK2 phosphorylation of free 'unloaded' MCM2-7 promotes nuclear exclusion of CDT1 – MCM2-7 thereby preventing DNA reduplication (Yeeles et al., 2015). However, once MCM2-7 is loaded at origins, phosphorylation by CDK2 functions to promote full helicase activation (reviewed in (Tanaka & Araki, 2013)).

6.9. Leading Strand Synthesis

Replication of the leading strand is performed by a stable complex between DNA polymerase epsilon (Pol ϵ) and the CMG complex (Zhou et al., 2017). Efficient leading strand replication requires the sliding DNA clamp Proliferation Cell Nuclear Antigen (PCNA), Replication Factor C (RFC), Claspin (orthologue of yeast Mrc1) (Yeeles et al., 2017) and possibly several additional proteins (reviewed in (Pellegrini & Costa, 2016; Burgers & Kunkel, 2017; Smits et al., 2019)). The CTF18 – RFC complex in combination with Pol ϵ is required for the efficient loading of PCNA (Fujisawa et al., 2017; Grabarczyk, Silkenat & Kisker, 2018).

6.10. Lagging Strand Synthesis

DNA polymerase alpha (Pol α), which is recruited by MCM10 and AND1 (CTF4 in yeast) to the lagging strand, is primarily responsible for initiation of lagging strand DNA synthesis. However, unlike the leading strand, DNA synthesis on the lagging strand occurs in the opposite direction to the growing replication fork. To account for this, a series of RNA primers are used as templates, which are read by the Pol α – RNA primase complex. This complex completes the synthesis of ~20-30 nucleotides before terminating and creating a series of Okazaki fragments. Extension and completion of Okazaki fragments is then performed by Pol delta (Pol δ), with ligation of fragments performed by DNA ligase and Fen1 (reviewed in (Pellegrini & Costa, 2016; Burgers & Kunkel, 2017)). Recent evidence suggests proteins that interact exclusively with the lagging strand do not block CMG translocation or replisome progression, while protein blocks that bind both strands do result in replication slowing (Kose et al., 2019).

6.11. DNA polymerase alpha (Pol α)

DNA polymerase alpha (Pol α) contains four subunits: POLA1, POLA2, PRIM1 and PRIM2. Its primary role is to initiate DNA synthesis and to extend RNA primers generated by DNA primase at origins and on Okazaki

fragments (reviewed in (Pellegrini, 2012; Burgers & Kunkel, 2017)). Pol α in combination with MCM2 –AND1 also plays an important role in maintaining epigenetic marks by facilitating the transfer of parental Histone H3-H4 tetramers onto the lagging-strand during DNA replication (Gan et al., 2018).

6.12. DNA polymerase delta (Pol δ)

DNA polymerase delta (Pol δ) possesses intrinsic 3 prime to 5 prime exonuclease activity. It binds to PCNA and helps process Okazaki fragment during lagging strand synthesis. This allows the subsequent ligation of fragments by FEN1 and DNA ligase, thereby completing lagging strand synthesis (reviewed in (Lujan, Williams & Kunkel, 2016; Stodola & Burgers, 2018)).

6.13. FEN1 DNA Ligase

Completion of lagging strand synthesis requires the processing of tens of millions of Okazaki fragments created during lagging strand replication. This process involves the removal of the RNA/DNA primers and the joining of Okazaki fragments. This is carried out by flap endonuclease 1 (FEN1), polymerase δ , the PCNA clamp and DNA ligase I (reviewed in (Zheng & Shen, 2011; Stodola & Burgers, 2016; Zaher et al., 2018)). Notably, PARP1 acts as a sensor for unligated Okazaki fragments during S phase, recruiting XRCC1 to promote DNA repair (Hanzlikova et al., 2018).

7. The S-phase Checkpoint

7.1. ATR and the S-phase checkpoint

Ataxia telangiectasia and Rad3-related protein (ATR) is a serine/threonine-protein kinase that plays an essential role in sensing single-stranded DNA (ssDNA) damage and mediating the cell cycle checkpoint response to replication stress during S-phase (Toledo et al., 2013; Saldivar et al., 2017). In addition, ATR and CHK1, play important roles during normal DNA replication to limit dormant origin firing (Moiseeva et al., 2019) and ensure that cells do not prematurely enter G2/M phase before replication is complete (Saldivar et al., 2018). Under conditions of stress, ATR works in conjunction with additional checkpoint proteins including RAD52 (Sotiriou et al., 2016), RAD51, BRCA1/2, and PARP1 (reviewed in (Rickman & Smogorzewska, 2019)). The mitotic regulators TPX2 and Aurora A have also been implicated in regulating replication stress by counteracting 53BP1 (Byrum et al., 2019), to ensure that inherited under-replicated DNA is efficiently repaired in the following cell cycle (Spies et al., 2019).

7.2. ETAA1 - ATRIP

ETAA1 (Ewing's tumour-associated antigen 1) plays an important role in recruiting ATR to sites of single stranded DNA (ssDNA) created during lagging strand synthesis, thereby helping to ensure fork progression during normal replication and during replication stress. The dual RPA-binding motifs within ETAA1 bind to RPA coated ssDNA,

where it directly interacts and stimulates ATR kinase activity (Bass et al., 2016; Haahr et al., 2016). This pathway is independent of the TOPBP1 and ATRIP (Rao et al., 2018), which can also recruit and activate ATR to RPA-coated ssDNA on the replicating lagging DNA strand ((Liu et al., 2011) and reviewed in (Saldivar, Cortez & Cimprich, 2017)).

7.3. Replication Protein A (RPA)

Replication Protein A (RPA) binds to single stranded DNA (ssDNA), which is created during the replication dependent unwinding of the DNA helix. This prevents the ssDNA from forming secondary structures and also promotes the recruitment of ATR through ETAA1 and ATRIP to ensure dormant origins fire in response to replication stress and to prevent premature firing of late origins of replication ((Toledo et al., 2013) and reviewed in (Saldivar, Cortez & Cimprich, 2017; Bhat & Cortez, 2018)). RPA also binds histone H3 and H4, helping to ensure efficient deposition of histones into the newly replicated DNA (Liu et al., 2017).

7.4. Multisite phosphorylation of CHK1 by ATR

During G1/S, growth factor signalling combined with p90 RSK phosphorylates CHK1 promoting its nuclear localization (Li et al., 2012). At sites of RPA coated ssDNA, ATR can phosphorylate CHK1 on S-317 and S-345, which activates CHK1 kinase activity (Zhao & Piwnicka-Worms, 2001; Wilsker et al., 2008). CHK1 functions to suppress firing of new origins in unreplicated areas in response to incompletely replicated or damaged DNA, and prevents premature firing of late origins of replication ensuring that the order and timing of replication occurs correctly by suppressing CDK2 activity (Katsuno et al., 2009; Petermann, Woodcock & Helleday, 2010; Ge & Blow, 2010).

7.5. Autophosphorylation of CHK1 on S-296

CHK1 autophosphorylation at S-296 is critical for S-phase checkpoint signalling by ATR, although its role in unperturbed replication is unclear (Li et al., 2012). S-296 phosphorylation creates a binding site for 14-3-3, which promotes the nuclear retention of CHK1 and maintenance of the checkpoint response, with failure to phosphorylate this site resulting in premature mitotic entry (Kasahara et al., 2010). Both TopBP1 and Claspin facilitate ATR mediated phosphorylation of CHK1 during replication (Liu et al., 2006).

8. Progression through S-phase

8.1. Phosphorylation of MCM3 on S-205 by CHK1

CHK1 phosphorylates MCM3 at S-205. This phosphorylation plays a role in regulating DNA replication track length under normal conditions. Under replication stress this phosphorylation is reduced, resulting in the generation of single strand DNA (ssDNA) and subsequent activation of ATR kinase (Han et al., 2015). The other components of the MCM2-7 hexamer are also heavily

phosphorylated during S-phase, with CHK1 regulation of Protein phosphatase 1 (PP1) playing a key role in removal of DDK-mediated phosphosites on MCM4 (Alver et al., 2017).

8.2. Multisite phosphorylation on NPAT by Cyclin E – CDK2
Cyclin E – CDK2 phosphorylates several sites on NPAT (S-775, S-779, S-1100, T-1270 and T-1350), which activates transcription of the histone H2B promoter and links DNA replication to histone gene transcription (Ma et al., 2000; Wei, Jin & Harper, 2003; Ye et al., 2003). Notably, NPAT appears to be primarily associated with Cyclin E2 rather than E1 (Rogers et al., 2015).

8.3. Histone transcription

NPAT recruits the TRRAP – Tip60 complex to histone gene promoters to coordinate the transcriptional activation of multiple histone genes during the G1/S-phase transition (DeRan et al., 2008). Its localization is also controlled by Cpn10, which is required for targeting NPAT to Histone Locus Bodies (HLB) and modulating histone transcription ((Ling Zheng et al., 2015) and reviewed in (Duronio & Marzluff, 2017)).

8.4. B-MYB expression

B-MYB expression is promoted by the E2F1-3 family of transcription factors during G1/S (Hanada et al., 2006). B-MYB in concert with MuvB is responsible for driving transcription of genes required for S/G2 phase progression including Cyclin A (CCNA2) ((Sadasivam, Duan & DeCaprio, 2012) and reviewed in (Joaquin & Watson, 2003)). Activation of B-MYB transcription requires multistep and multisite phosphorylation by CDK2 and PLK1 (Ziebold et al., 1997; Werwein et al., 2018).

8.5. B-MYB – MuvB multisite phosphorylation

Activation of B-MYB transcription requires multistep and multisite phosphorylation by CDK2 and PLK1 (Ziebold et al., 1997; Werwein et al., 2018).

8.6. Phosphorylation of Cyclin E on S-384 by CDK2

CDK2 was originally thought to auto-phosphorylate Cyclin E1 (CCNE1) on T-380 (Won & Reed, 1996), however this was later shown to be performed by GSK3 with CDK2 auto-phosphorylating the neighbouring S-384 site (Welcker et al., 2003). Notably PP2A-B56 dephosphorylates the autophosphorylation site S-384 on CCNE1 (Cyclin E) preventing efficient FBW7 binding and subsequent degradation of Cyclin E during G1/S phase (Davis et al., 2017). Interestingly, overexpression of PP2A-B55 β has been linked with stabilization and accumulation of Cyclin E in cancer, suggesting that there may be some redundancy between PP2A B55 and B56 complexes (Tan et al., 2014).

8.7. Phosphorylation of Cyclin E on T-380 by GSK3

Phosphorylation of T-380 by GSK3 promotes SCF – FBW7 binding and degradation of Cyclin E. Several additional phosphorylation sites including T-62, and S-372 appear to regulate Cyclin E1 degradation, with CDK2 dependent

autophosphorylation of S-384 required for efficient FBW7 binding and ubiquitination of Cyclin E (Welcker et al., 2003).

8.8. Degradation of Cyclin E

Multisite phosphorylation of Cyclin E1 on T-380 and S-384 creates a high affinity binding site for FBW7 (F-box and WD repeat domain-containing 7), a component of the SKP1-cullin-F-box ubiquitin protein ligase complex (Hao et al., 2007). This process is dependent on Pin1 mediated isomerization of the T-380/S-384 motif, and FBW7 dimerization, which enhance its binding and sequestration of Cyclin E to the nucleolus for ubiquitination and degradation (Bhaskaran et al., 2013; Welcker et al., 2013). Notably, FBW7 functions as a tumour suppressor, with loss of FBW7 causing aberrant overexpression of Cyclin E, which in turn leads to increased chromosomal instability and cancer (Welcker & Clurman, 2008; Takada et al., 2017).

8.9. Cyclin A transcription by B-MYB – MuvB

B-MYB – MuvB promotes the expression genes required for S/G2 phase progression, including Cyclin A2 (CCNA2) (Bartusel, Schubert & Klempnauer, 2005; Pilkinton et al., 2007).

8.10. Cyclin A binding to CDK2

Cyclin A binds to CDK2 during S-phase and enables its activation by inducing a conformational change that opens up the active site of the kinase (Jeffrey et al., 1995).

8.11. CDK2 multisite phosphorylation of E2F1

Cyclin A – CDK2 binds to and phosphorylates E2F1, inhibiting its DNA-binding activity, thereby ensuring timely progression through S-phase (Xu et al., 1994; Krek, Xu & Livingston, 1995). Cyclin A – CDK2 binding also limits E2F1 binding to p53, thereby blocking p53 dependent apoptosis (Hsieh et al., 2002). Finally, E2F1 can also be targeted for destruction by several other kinases including CDK7, GSK3 and p38 MAPK, which can phosphorylate S-403 and T-433 (Vandel & Kouzarides, 1999; García-Alvarez et al., 2007; Ivanova, Nakrieko & Dagnino, 2009). Of note, Cyclin A – CDK2 may potentially phosphorylate 180 additional substrates spanning multiple pathways including centrosome duplication, metabolism, ribosome function and DNA replication and repair (Chi et al., 2008; Kanakkanthara et al., 2016).

8.12. CHK1 multisite phosphorylation of Treslin

CHK1 binds and phosphorylates Treslin (TICRR) on seven potential sites, with S-1893/T-1897 likely the primary sites. These phosphorylations negatively regulate the replication-initiating function of Treslin, inhibiting Treslin mediated loading of CDC45 onto potential origins of replication (Guo et al., 2015).

8.13. CHK1 multisite phosphorylation of E2F6

Replication stress induces CHK1 phosphorylation of E2F6 on S-12 and S-52, blocking E2F6 DNA binding. This allows

E2F1-3 to re-bind DNA and promote E2F dependent transcription of G1/S genes (Bertoli et al., 2013). In addition, CHK1 can also phosphorylate E2F7 and E2F8, which promotes 14-3-3 recruitment and subsequent disruption of the repressive transcriptional functions of these E2Fs (Yuan et al., 2018). E2F6-8 do not require pocket proteins for their repressor activity, but they appear to be required to turn off G1/S transcription during S-phase to prevent re-expression of G1/S proteins. They achieve this by binding to E2F1-3 promoters and preventing the transcription of G1/S genes (Giangrande et al., 2004; Christensen et al., 2005; Westendorp et al., 2012).

8.14. CHK1 multisite phosphorylation of CDC25

CHK1 plays an important role in controlling proper S-phase exit via inhibitory phosphorylation of CDC25. CHK1 phosphorylates both CDC25A and CDC25B. CDC25A is phosphorylated on multiple sites (including S-76, S-124, S-178), targeting CDC25A phosphatase for destruction in response to DNA damage or replication stress (Zhao, Watkins & Piwnica-Worms, 2002; Sørensen et al., 2003; Jin et al., 2003). This helps to ensure CDK1 activity remains limited until replication is complete (Lemmens et al., 2018). Several other kinases can also regulate CDC25A destruction including GSK3 (Kang et al., 2008), CK1 (Honaker & Piwnica-Worms, 2010) and NEK11 (Melixetian et al., 2009). CDC25B is phosphorylated by CHK1 during an unperturbed S-phase on S-230 blocking CDC25B activity (Schmitt et al., 2006).

9. Completion of S-phase and entry into Early G2 phase

9.1. Cyclin A binding to CDK1

Cyclin A binds to CDK1 during G2-phase and its activity is required to promote mitotic entry by activating the BORA – Aurora A – PLK1 pathway that promotes CDC25 dependent removal of inhibitory Y-15 and T-14 phosphorylations on Cyclin B – CDK1 (Vigneron et al., 2018). Cyclin A – CDK1 also phosphorylates up to one hundred and fifty six additional substrates during G2/M including Myosin phosphatase targeting subunit 1 (MYPT1), which plays an important role in regulating kinetochore-microtubule stability during mitosis (Dumitru et al., 2017).

9.2. CDK1/2 multisite phosphorylation of CHK1

CDK1 and CDK2 can phosphorylate CHK1 on S-286 and S-301, promoting its export from the nucleus. Phosphorylation on S-286 and S-301 by CDK1 promotes nuclear export of CHK1 prior to mitosis, thereby allowing full activation of CDK1 activity required for mitotic entry (Shiromizu et al., 2006; Enomoto et al., 2009). During late S-phase Cyclin A – CDK activity also promotes increased CDH1 levels, which targets Claspin, a positive regulator of ATR mediated phosphorylation of CHK1, thereby reducing CHK1 activity (Oakes et al., 2014; Burgess, 2015).

9.3. Multisite phosphorylation of B-MYB – MuvB by CDK2

B-MYB is phosphorylated on multiple residues (including T-447, T-490, and T-497 and S-581) during S phase by Cyclin A – CDK2. This promotes the subsequent ubiquitination and degradation of B-MYB (Ziebold et al., 1997; Charrasse et al., 2000; Müller-Tidow et al., 2001). MuvB and B-MYB recruit FOXM1 to late gene promoters during S/G2, with both MuvB and FOXM1 remaining on promoters after B-MYB is phosphorylated and degraded during late S-phase (Sadasivam, Duan & DeCaprio, 2012; Down et al., 2012). The Cdc34 – SCF – p45 – Skp2 ubiquitin pathway is responsible for mediating the ubiquitination and degradation of B-MYB during S phase (Charrasse et al., 2000).

9.4. Recruitment of FOXM1 to MuvB and phosphorylation by CDK1

FOXM1 is recruited to MuvB during late S-Phase (Sadasivam, Duan & DeCaprio, 2012). Phosphorylation of FOXM1 by CDK1 promotes transcription of genes required for late S/G2/M progression by the FOXM1 – MuvB complex (Chen et al., 2009; Saldivar et al., 2018). Notably, ATR limits CDK phosphorylation until DNA replication is complete to prevent premature entry into mitosis with under-replicated DNA. The phosphorylation by CDK1 is required for subsequent binding of PLK1, which further phosphorylates and activates FOXM1 transcriptional activity (Fu et al., 2008).

9.5. Cyclin B transcription

FOXM1 – MuvB drives the transcription of a large number of late cell cycle genes required for G2/M progression. These include Cyclin B (CCNB1-3), along with other key proteins including ubiquitin-conjugating enzyme E2C (UBE2C; also known as UBCH10), centromere protein E (CENPE) and polo-like kinase 1 (PLK1) (Sadasivam, Duan & DeCaprio, 2012; Fischer et al., 2016).

9.6. Cyclin B binding to CDK1

There are three main isoforms of Cyclin B (CCNB1-3), with Cyclin B1 and B2 the major mitotic cyclins in mammalian somatic cells, while less is known about Cyclin B3, although it is highly expressed in the testis (Lozano et al., 2002). Similar to Cyclin A, binding of Cyclin B to CDK1 promotes a conformation change in CDK1 that opens up the active site of the kinase, which is essential for allowing substrate access (Brown et al., 2015). Cyclin B1 is essential for mitotic entry, while Cyclin B2 appears to play important roles in regulating centrosome separation by regulating Aurora A and PLK1 activity (Nam & van Deursen, 2014).

9.7. Phosphorylation of CDK1 on Y-15 by WEE1

Once DNA replication is complete, the cell begins preparing for mitosis during G2 phase and marks the start of the adjoining SnapShot: Phosphoregulation of Mitosis (Burgess et al., 2017). Here both WEE1 and MYT1 kinases phosphorylate CDK1 on Y-15 and T-14 respectively, inhibiting the activity of Cyclin B – CDK1 during G2 in order to prevent premature mitotic entry (McGowan & Russell,

1993; Booher, Holman & Fattaey, 1997). Failure to phosphorylate and inactivate CDK1 results in cells attempting to prematurely enter mitosis during S-phase, resulting in embryonic lethality (Szmyd et al., 2019). Activation of Cyclin B – CDK1 requires Cyclin A – CDK1 phosphorylation of Bora, triggering Aurora-A activation of PLK1 and subsequent phosphorylation of CDC25, which then removes Y-15 and T-14 phosphorylations on Cyclin B – CDK1 (Vigneron et al., 2018).

References

- Abbas T, Jha S, Sherman NE, Dutta A 2007. Autocatalytic Phosphorylation of CDK2 at the Activating Thr160. *Cell Cycle* 6:843–852. DOI: 10.4161/cc.6.7.4000.
- Abid Ali F, Douglas ME, Locke J, Pye VE, Nans A, Diffley JFX, Costa A 2017. Cryo-EM structure of a licensed DNA replication origin. *Nat Commun* 8:2241. DOI: 10.1038/s41467-017-02389-0.
- Alver RC, Chadha GS, Gillespie PJ, Blow JJ 2017. Reversal of DDK-Mediated MCM Phosphorylation by Rif1-PP1 Regulates Replication Initiation and Replisome Stability Independently of ATR/Chk1. *Cell reports* 18:2508–2520. DOI: 10.1016/j.celrep.2017.02.042.
- An X, Ng SS, Xie D, Zeng Y-X, Sze J, Wang J, Chen YC, Chow BKC, Lu G, Poon WS, Kung H-F, Wong BCY, Lin MC-M 2010. Functional characterisation of cell cycle-related kinase (CCRK) in colorectal cancer carcinogenesis. *European Journal of Cancer* 46:1752–1761.
- Arbi M, Pefani D-E, Taraviras S, Lygerou Z 2018. Controlling centriole numbers: Geminin family members as master regulators of centriole amplification and multiciliogenesis. *Chromosoma* 127:151–174. DOI: 10.1007/s00412-017-0652-7.
- Arquint C, Nigg EA 2016. The PLK4-STIL-SAS-6 module at the core of centriole duplication. *Biochemical Society Transactions* 44:1253–1263. DOI: 10.1042/BST20160116.
- Arquint C, Gabryjczyk A-M, Imseng S, Böhm R, Sauer E, Hiller S, Nigg EA, Maier T 2015. STIL binding to Polo-box 3 of PLK4 regulates centriole duplication. *eLife* 4:1948. DOI: 10.7554/eLife.07888.
- Aydogan MG, Wainman A, Saurya S, Steinacker TL, Caballe A, Novak ZA, Baumbach J, Muschalik N, Raff JW 2018. A homeostatic clock sets daughter centriole size in flies. *J Cell Biol* 217:1233–1248. DOI: 10.1083/jcb.201801014.
- Bachs O, Gallastegui E, Orlando S, Bigas A, Morante-Redolat JM, Serratos J, Fariñas I, Aligué R, Pujol MJ 2018. Role of p27 Kip1 as a transcriptional regulator. *Oncotarget* 9:26259–26278. DOI: 10.18632/oncotarget.25447.
- Bagui TK, Mohapatra S, Haura E, Pledger WJ 2003. P27Kip1 and p21Cip1 are not required for the formation of active D cyclin-cdk4 complexes. *Molecular and cellular biology* 23:7285–7290. DOI: 10.1128/mcb.23.20.7285-7290.2003.
- Barbash O, Egan E, Pontano LL, Kosak J, Diehl JA 2009. Lysine 269 is essential for cyclin D1 ubiquitylation by the SCF^{Fbx4/αB-crystallin} ligase and subsequent proteasome-dependent degradation. *Oncogene* 28:4317–4325. DOI: 10.1038/nc.2009.287.
- Bartusel T, Schubert S, Klempnauer K-H 2005. Regulation of the cyclin D1 and cyclin A1 promoters by B-Myb is mediated by Sp1 binding sites. *Gene* 351:171–180. DOI: 10.1016/j.gene.2005.03.035.
- Bass TE, Luzwick JW, Kavanaugh G, Carroll C, Dungrawala H, Glick GG, Feldkamp MD, Putney R, Chazin WJ, Cortez D 2016. ETAA1 acts at stalled replication forks to maintain genome integrity. *Nature Cell Biology* 18:1185–1195. DOI: 10.1038/ncb3415.
- Bellelli R, Belan O, Pye VE, Clement C, Maslen SL, Skehel JM, Cherepanov P, Almouzni G, Boulton SJ 2018a. POLE3-POLE4 Is a Histone H3-H4 Chaperone that Maintains Chromatin Integrity during DNA Replication. *Molecular cell* 72:112–126.e5.
- Bellelli R, Borel V, Logan C, Svendsen J, Cox DE, Nye E, Metcalfe K, O'Connell SM, Stamp G, Flynn HR, Snijders AP, Lassailly F, Jackson A, Boulton SJ 2018b. Pole Instability Drives Replication Stress, Abnormal Development, and Tumorigenesis. *Molecular cell* 70:707–721.e7.
- Benzeno S, Lu F, Guo M, Barbash O, Zhang F, Herman JG, Klein PS, Rustgi A, Diehl JA 2006. Identification of mutations that disrupt phosphorylation-dependent nuclear export of cyclin D1. *Oncogene* 25:6291–6303. DOI: 10.1038/sj.onc.1209644.
- Bertoli C, Klier S, McGowan C, Wittenberg C, de Bruin RAM 2013. Chk1 Inhibits E2F6 Repressor Function in Response to Replication Stress to Maintain Cell-Cycle Transcription. *Current Biology* 23:1629–1637. DOI: 10.1016/j.cub.2013.06.063.
- Bertoli C, Skotheim JM, de Bruin RAM 2013. Control of cell cycle transcription during G1 and S phases. *Nature reviews. Molecular cell biology* 14:518–528. DOI: 10.1038/nrm3629.
- Bhaskaran N, van Drogen F, Ng H-F, Kumar R, Ekholm-Reed S, Peter M, Sangfelt O, Reed SI 2013. Fbw7α and Fbw7γ collaborate to shuttle cyclin E1 into the nucleolus for multiubiquitylation. *Molecular and cellular biology* 33:85–97. DOI: 10.1128/MCB.00288-12.
- Bisteau X, Paternot S, Colleoni B, Ecker K, Coulonval K, De Groote P, Declercq W, Hengst L, Roger PP 2013. CDK4 T172 Phosphorylation Is Central in a CDK7-Dependent Bidirectional CDK4/CDK2 Interplay Mediated by p21 Phosphorylation at the Restriction Point. *PLoS Genetics* 9:e1003546. DOI: 10.1371/journal.pgen.1003546.
- Bockstaele L, Kooken H, Libert F, Paternot S, Dumont JE, de Launoit Y, Roger PP, Coulonval K 2006. Regulated activating Thr172 phosphorylation of cyclin-dependent kinase 4(CDK4): its relationship with cyclins and CDK "inhibitors". *Molecular and cellular biology* 26:5070–5085. DOI: 10.1128/MCB.02006-05.
- Booher RN, Holman PS, Fattaey A 1997. Human Myt1 is a cell cycle-regulated kinase that inhibits Cdc2 but not Cdk2 activity. *The Journal of biological chemistry* 272:22300–22306.
- Boos D, Yekezare M, Diffley JFX 2013. Identification of a heteromeric complex that promotes DNA replication origin firing in human cells. *Science* 340:981–984. DOI: 10.1126/science.1237448.
- Bornstein G, Bloom J, Sitry-Shevah D, Nakayama K, Pagano M, Hershko A 2003. Role of the SCFSkp2 ubiquitin ligase in the degradation of p21Cip1 in S phase. *The Journal of biological chemistry* 278:25752–25757. DOI: 10.1074/jbc.M301774200.
- Branzei D, Foiani M 2010. Maintaining genome stability at the replication fork. *Nature reviews. Molecular cell biology* 11:208–219. DOI: 10.1038/nrm2852.
- Brown NR, Korolchuk S, Martin MP, Stanley WA, Moukhametzianov R, Noble MEM, Endicott JA 2015. CDK1 structures reveal conserved and unique features of the essential cell cycle CDK. *Nat Commun* 6:6769. DOI: 10.1038/ncomms7769.
- Brown NR, Noble ME, Lawrie AM, Morris MC, Tunnah P, Divita G, Johnson LN, Endicott JA 1999. Effects of phosphorylation of threonine 160 on cyclin-dependent kinase 2 structure and activity. *The Journal of biological chemistry* 274:8746–8756. DOI: 10.1074/jbc.274.13.8746.
- Bruck I, Kaplan D 2009. Dbf4-Cdc7 phosphorylation of Mcm2 is required for cell growth. *The Journal of biological chemistry* 284:28823–28831. DOI: 10.1074/jbc.M109.039123.
- Bruck I, Kaplan DL 2015. Conserved mechanism for coordinating replication fork helicase assembly with phosphorylation of the helicase. *Proc Natl Acad Sci USA* 112:11223–11228. DOI: 10.1073/pnas.1509608112.
- Burgers PMJ, Kunkel TA 2017. Eukaryotic DNA Replication Fork. *Annual review of biochemistry* 86:417–438. DOI: 10.1146/annurev-biochem-061516-044709.
- Burgess A 2015. Degrading Claspin away with Cdh1 and Cyclin A. *Cell Cycle* 14:171–171. DOI: 10.4161/15384101.2014.989949.
- Burgess A, Vuong J, Rogers S, Malumbres M, O'Donoghue SI 2017. SnapShot: Phosphoregulation of Mitosis. *Cell* 169:1358–1358.e1. DOI: 10.1016/j.cell.2017.06.003.
- Burgess A., J. Vuong, K. A. Marzec, U. N. de Lichtenberg, S. I. O'Donoghue and L. J. Jensen 2019. "SnapShot: S-phase Entry and Exit." Cell in press.
- Byrum AK, Carvajal-Maldonado D, Mudge MC, Valle-Garcia D, Majid MC, Patel R, Sowa ME, Gygi SP, Harper JW, Shi Y, Vindigni A, Mosammamaparast N 2019. Mitotic regulators TPX2 and Aurora A protect DNA forks during replication stress by counteracting 53BP1 function. *J Cell Biol* 218:422–432. DOI: 10.1083/jcb.201803003.

- Champasa K, Blank C, Friedman LJ, Gelles J, Bell SP, Botchan MR. 2019. A conserved Mcm4 motif is required for Mcm2-7 double-hexamer formation and origin DNA unwinding. *eLife* 8:e45538. doi:10.7554/eLife.45538
- Charrasse S, Carena I, Brondani V, Klemmpauer K-H, Ferrari S 2000. Degradation of B-Myb by ubiquitin-mediated proteolysis: involvement of the Cdc34-SCF p45Skp2 pathway. *Oncogene* 19:2986–2995. DOI: 10.1038/sj.onc.1203618.
- Charrasse S, Gharbi-Ayachi A, Burgess A, Vera J, Hached K, Raynaud P, Schwob E, Lorca T, Castro A 2017. Ensa controls S-phase length by modulating Treslin levels. *Nat Commun* 8:206. DOI: 10.1038/s41467-017-00339-4.
- Chen Y-J, Dominguez-Brauer C, Wang Z, Asara JM, Costa RH, Tyner AL, Lau LF, Raychaudhuri P 2009. A Conserved Phosphorylation Site within the Forkhead Domain of FoxM1B Is Required for Its Activation by Cyclin-CDK1. *Journal of Biological Chemistry* 284:30695–30707.
- Cheng M, Olivier P, Diehl JA, Fero M, Roussel MF, Roberts JM, Sherr CJ 1999. The p21(Cip1) and p27(Kip1) CDK “inhibitors” are essential activators of cyclin D-dependent kinases in murine fibroblasts. *The EMBO Journal* 18:1571–1583. DOI: 10.1093/emboj/18.6.1571.
- Chi Y, Welcker M, Hizli AA, Posakony JJ, Aebersold R, Clurman BE 2008. Identification of CDK2 substrates in human cell lysates. *Genome Biology* 9:R149. DOI: 10.1186/gb-2008-9-10-r149.
- Christensen J, Cloos P, Toftegaard U, Klinkenberg D, Bracken AP, Trinh E, Heeran M, Di Stefano L, Helin K 2005. Characterization of E2F8, a novel E2F-like cell-cycle regulated repressor of E2F-activated transcription. *Nucleic acids research* 33:5458–5470.
- Chu I, Sun J, Arnaout A, Kahn H, Hanna W, Narod S, Sun P, Tan C-K, Hengst L, Slingerland J 2007. p27 Phosphorylation by Src Regulates Inhibition of Cyclin E-Cdk2. *Cell* 128:281–294. DOI: 10.1016/j.cell.2006.11.049.
- Coleman KG, Wautlet BS, Morrissey D, Mulheron J, Sedman SA, Brinkley P, Price S, Webster KR 1997. Identification of CDK4 sequences involved in cyclin D1 and p16 binding. *The Journal of biological chemistry* 272:18869–18874.
- Colleoni B, Paternot S, Pita JM, Bisteau X, Coulonval K, Davis RJ, Raspé E, Roger PP 2017. JNKs function as CDK4-activating kinases by phosphorylating CDK4 and p21. *Oncogene* 36:4349–4361. DOI: 10.1038/onc.2017.7.
- Cunha-Ferreira I, Bento I, Pimenta-Marques A, Jana SC, Lince-Faria M, Duarte P, Borrego-Pinto J, Gilberto S, Amado T, Brito D, Rodrigues-Martins A, Debski J, Dzhinzhev N, Bettencourt-Dias M 2013. Regulation of Autophosphorylation Controls PLK4 Self-Destruction and Centriole Number. *Current Biology* 23:2245–2254. DOI: 10.1016/j.cub.2013.09.037.
- Dang CV, O’Donnell KA, Zeller KI, Nguyen T, Osthus RC, Li F 2006. The c-Myc target gene network. *25 years of the c-Myc oncogene* 16:253–264. DOI: 10.1016/j.semcancer.2006.07.014.
- Das RK, Huang Y, Phillips AH, Kriwacki RW, Pappu RV 2016. Cryptic sequence features within the disordered protein p27Kip1 regulate cell cycle signaling. *Proc Natl Acad Sci USA* 113:5616–5621. DOI: 10.1073/pnas.1516277113.
- Davé A, Cooley C, Garg M, Bianchi A 2014. Protein Phosphatase 1 Recruitment by Rif1 Regulates DNA Replication Origin Firing by Counteracting DDK Activity. *Cell reports* 7:53–61. DOI: 10.1016/j.celrep.2014.02.019.
- Davis RJ, Swanger J, Hughes BT, Clurman BE 2017. The PP2A-B56 Phosphatase Opposes Cyclin E Autocatalytic Degradation via Site-Specific Dephosphorylation. *Molecular and cellular biology* 37:e00657–16. DOI: 10.1128/MCB.00657-16.
- Deegan TD, Yeeles JT, Diffley JF 2016. Phosphopeptide binding by Sld3 links Dbf4-dependent kinase to MCM replicative helicase activation. *The EMBO Journal* 35:961–973. DOI: 10.15252/embj.201593552.
- DeGregori J, Kowalik T, Nevins JR 1995. Cellular targets for activation by the E2F1 transcription factor include DNA synthesis- and G1/S-regulatory genes. *Molecular and cellular biology* 15:4215–4224. DOI: 10.1128/mcb.15.8.4215.
- DeRan M, Pulvino M, Greene E, Su C, Zhao J 2008. Transcriptional activation of histone genes requires NPAT-dependent recruitment of TRRAP-Tip60 complex to histone promoters during the G1/S phase transition. *Molecular and cellular biology* 28:435–447. DOI: 10.1128/MCB.00607-07.
- Diehl JA, Zindy F, Sherr CJ 1997. Inhibition of cyclin D1 phosphorylation on threonine-286 prevents its rapid degradation via the ubiquitin-proteasome pathway. *Genes & Development* 11:957–972. DOI: 10.1101/gad.11.8.957.
- Dong P, Maddali MV, Srimani JK, Thélot F, Nevins JR, Mathey-Prevot B, You L 2014. Division of labour between Myc and G1 cyclins in cell cycle commitment and pace control. *Nat Commun* 5:4750. DOI: 10.1038/ncomms5750.
- Dong P, Zhang C, Parker B-T, You L, Mathey-Prevot B 2018. Cyclin D/CDK4/6 activity controls G1 length in mammalian cells. *PLoS ONE* 13:e0185637. DOI: 10.1371/journal.pone.0185637.
- Douglas ME, Abid Ali F, Costa A, Diffley JFX 2018. The mechanism of eukaryotic CMG helicase activation. *Nature* 555:265–268.
- Down CF, Millour J, Lam EWF, Watson RJ 2012. Binding of FoxM1 to G2/M gene promoters is dependent upon B-Myb. *Biochimica et Biophysica Acta (BBA) - Gene Regulatory Mechanisms* 1819:855–862.
- Dozier C, Mazzolini L, Cénac C, Froment C, Burlet-Schiltz O, Besson A, Manenti S 2017. CyclinD-CDK4/6 complexes phosphorylate CDC25A and regulate its stability. *Oncogene* 36:3781–3788. DOI: 10.1038/onc.2016.506.
- Duman-Scheel M, Weng L, Xin S, Du W 2002. Hedgehog regulates cell growth and proliferation by inducing Cyclin D and Cyclin E. *Nature* 417:299–304. DOI: 10.1038/417299a.
- Dumitru AMG, Rusin SF, Clark AEM, Kettenbach AN, Compton DA 2017. Cyclin A/Cdk1 modulates Plk1 activity in prometaphase to regulate kinetochore-microtubule attachment stability. *eLife* 6:ra42. DOI: 10.7554/eLife.29303.
- Duronio RJ, Marzluff WF 2017. Coordinating cell cycle-regulated histone gene expression through assembly and function of the Histone Locus Body. *RNA Biology* 14:726–738. DOI: 10.1080/15476286.2016.1265198.
- Dzhinzhev NS, Tzolovsky G, Lipinski Z, Abdelaziz M, Debski J, Dadlez M, Glover DM 2017. Two-step phosphorylation of Ana2 by Plk4 is required for the sequential loading of Ana2 and Sas6 to initiate procentriole formation. *Open biology* 7:170247. DOI: 10.1098/rsob.170247.
- Dzhinzhev NS, Tzolovsky G, Lipinski Z, Schneider S, Lattao R, Fu J, Debski J, Dadlez M, Glover DM 2014. Plk4 Phosphorylates Ana2 to Trigger Sas6 Recruitment and Procentriole Formation. *Current Biology* 24:2526–2532. DOI: 10.1016/j.cub.2014.08.061.
- Dzhinzhev NS, Yu QD, Weiskopf K, Tzolovsky G, Cunha-Ferreira I, Riparbelli M, Rodrigues-Martins A, Bettencourt-Dias M, Callaini G, Glover DM 2010. Asterless is a scaffold for the onset of centriole assembly. *Nature* 467:714–718. DOI: 10.1038/nature09445.
- D’Angiolella V, Donato V, Vijayakumar S, Saraf A, Florens L, Washburn MP, Dynlacht B, Pagano M 2010. SCF^{sup}Cyclin F</sup> controls centrosome homeostasis and mitotic fidelity through CP110 degradation. *Nature* 466:138–142. DOI: 10.1038/nature09140.
- Enomoto M, Goto H, Tomono Y, Kasahara K, Tsujimura K, Kiyono T, Inagaki M 2009. Novel positive feedback loop between Cdk1 and Chk1 in the nucleus during G2/M transition. *The Journal of biological chemistry* 284:34223–34230. DOI: 10.1074/jbc.C109.051540.
- Evrin C, Clarke P, Zech J, Lurz R, Sun J, Uhle S, Li H, Stillman B, Speck C 2009. A double-hexameric MCM2-7 complex is loaded onto origin DNA during licensing of eukaryotic DNA replication. *Proc Natl Acad Sci USA* 106:20240–20245. DOI: 10.1073/pnas.0911500106.
- Ferguson RL, Pascreau G, Maller JL 2010. The cyclin A centrosomal localization sequence recruits MCM5 and Orc1 to regulate centrosome reduplication. *Journal of cell science* 123:2743–2749. DOI: 10.1242/jcs.073098.
- Fernández-Cid A, Riera A, Tognetti S, Herrera MC, Samel S, Evrin C, Winkler C, Gardenal E, Uhle S, Speck C 2013. An ORC/Cdc6/MCM2-7 Complex Is Formed in a Multistep Reaction to Serve as a Platform for MCM Double-Hexamer Assembly. *Molecular cell* 50:577–588. DOI: 10.1016/j.molcel.2013.03.026.
- Fischer M, Müller GA 2017. Cell cycle transcription control: DREAM/MuvB and RB-E2F complexes. *Critical Reviews in Biochemistry and Molecular Biology* 52:638–662. DOI: 10.1080/10409238.2017.1360836.

- Fischer M, Grossmann P, Padi M, DeCaprio JA 2016. Integration of TP53, DREAM, MMB-FOX1 and RB-E2F target gene analyses identifies cell cycle gene regulatory networks. *Nucleic acids research* 44:6070–6086. DOI: 10.1093/nar/gkw523.
- Fisher RP 2016. Getting to S: CDK functions and targets on the path to cell-cycle commitment. *F1000Research* 5:2374–7. DOI: 10.12688/f1000research.9463.1.
- Fleuren EDG, Zhang L, Wu J, Daly RJ 2016. The kinome “at large” in cancer. *Nature reviews. Cancer* 16:83–98. DOI: 10.1038/nrc.2015.18.
- Frigola J, He J, Kinkelin K, Pye VE, Renault L, Douglas ME, Remus D, Cherepanov P, Costa A, Diffley JFX 2017. Cdt1 stabilizes an open MCM ring for helicase loading. *Nat Commun* 8:15720. DOI: 10.1038/ncomms15720.
- Fu Z, Malureanu L, Huang J, Wang W, Li H, van Deursen JM, Tindall DJ, Chen J 2008. Plk1-dependent phosphorylation of FoxM1 regulates a transcriptional programme required for mitotic progression. *Nature Cell Biology* 10:1076–1082. DOI: 10.1038/ncb1767.
- Fujisawa R, Ohashi E, Hirota K, Tsurimoto T 2017. Human CTF18-RFC clamp-loader complexed with non-synthesising DNA polymerase ϵ efficiently loads the PCNA sliding clamp. *Nucleic acids research* 45:4550–4563.
- Furthesthal L, Swanson C, Kaiser BK, Eldridge AG, Jackson PK 2001. Triggering ubiquitination of a CDK inhibitor at origins of DNA replication. *Nature Cell Biology* 3:715–722. DOI: 10.1038/35087026.
- Galletta BJ, Fagerstrom CJ, Schoborg TA, McLamarrah TA, Ryniawec JM, Buster DW, Slep KC, Rogers GC, Rusan NM 2016. A centrosome interactome provides insight into organelle assembly and reveals a non-duplication role for Plk4. *Nat Commun* 7:12476. DOI: 10.1038/ncomms12476.
- Gan H, Serra-Cardona A, Hua X, Zhou H, Labib K, Yu C, Zhang Z 2018. The Mcm2-Ctf4-Pol α Axis Facilitates Parental Histone H3-H4 Transfer to Lagging Strands. *Molecular cell* 72:140–151.e3. DOI: 10.1016/j.molcel.2018.09.001.
- García-Alvarez G, Ventura V, Ros O, Aligué R, Gil J, Tauler A 2007. Glycogen synthase kinase-3 β binds to E2F1 and regulates its transcriptional activity. *Mitogen-Activated Protein Kinases: New Insights on Regulation, Function and Role in Human Disease* 1773:375–382. DOI: 10.1016/j.bbamcr.2006.09.015.
- Ge XQ, Blow JJ 2010. Chk1 inhibits replication factory activation but allows dormant origin firing in existing factories. *J Cell Biol* 191:1285–1297. DOI: 10.1083/jcb.201007074.
- Gennaro VJ, Stanek TJ, Peck AR, Sun Y, Wang F, Qie S, Knudsen KE, Rui H, Butt T, Diehl JA, McMahon SB 2018. Control of CCND1 ubiquitylation by the catalytic SAGA subunit USP22 is essential for cell cycle progression through G1 in cancer cells. *Proc Natl Acad Sci USA* 115:E9298–E9307. DOI: 10.1073/pnas.1807704115.
- Georgescu R, Yuan Z, Bai L, de Luna Almeida Santos R, Sun J, Zhang D, Yurieva O, Li H, O'Donnell ME 2017. Structure of eukaryotic CMG helicase at a replication fork and implications to replisome architecture and origin initiation. *Proc Natl Acad Sci USA* 114:E697–E706. DOI: 10.1073/pnas.1620500114.
- Giangrande PH, Zhu W, Schlisio S, Sun X, Mori S, Gaubatz S, Nevins JR 2004. A role for E2F6 in distinguishing G1/S- and G2/M-specific transcription. *Genes & Development* 18:2941–2951. DOI: 10.1101/gad.1239304.
- Grabarczyk DB, Silkenat S, Kisker C 2018. Structural Basis for the Recruitment of Ctf18-RFC to the Replisome. *Structure* 26:137–144.e3. DOI: 10.1016/j.str.2017.11.004.
- Grandori C, Cowley SM, James LP, Eisenman RN 2000. The Myc/Max/Mad Network and the Transcriptional Control of Cell Behavior. *Annu. Rev. Cell Dev. Biol.* 16:653–699. DOI: 10.1146/annurev.cellbio.16.1.653.
- Grant GD, Brooks L 3rd, Zhang X, Mahoney JM, Martyanov V, Wood TA, Sherlock G, Cheng C, Whitfield ML 2013. Identification of cell cycle-regulated genes periodically expressed in U2OS cells and their regulation by FOXM1 and E2F transcription factors. *MBoC* 24:3634–3650. DOI: 10.1091/mbc.e13-05-0264.
- Grimmler M, Wang Y, Mund T, Cilenšek Z, Keidel E-M, Waddell MB, Jäkel H, Kullmann M, Kriwacki RW, Hengst L 2007. Cdk-Inhibitory Activity and Stability of p27Kip1 Are Directly Regulated by Oncogenic Tyrosine Kinases. *Cell* 128:269–280.
- Gu Y, Rosenblatt J, Morgan DO 1992. Cell cycle regulation of CDK2 activity by phosphorylation of Thr160 and Tyr15. *The EMBO Journal* 11:3995–4005.
- Guo C, Kumagai A, Schlacher K, Shevchenko A, Shevchenko A, Dunphy WG 2015. Interaction of Chk1 with Treslin Negatively Regulates the Initiation of Chromosomal DNA Replication. *Molecular cell* 57:492–505.
- Haahr P, Hoffmann S, Tollenare MAX, Ho T, Toledo LI, Mann M, Bekker-Jensen S, Räschle M, Mailand N 2016. Activation of the ATR kinase by the RPA-binding protein ETAA1. *Nature Cell Biology* 18:1196–1207. DOI: 10.1038/ncb3422.
- Han X, Mayca Pozo F, Wisotsky JN, Wang B, Jacobberger JW, Zhang Y 2015. Phosphorylation of Minichromosome Maintenance 3 (MCM3) by Checkpoint Kinase 1 (Chk1) Negatively Regulates DNA Replication and Checkpoint Activation. *The Journal of biological chemistry* 290:12370–12378. DOI: 10.1074/jbc.M114.621532.
- Hanada N, Lo H-W, Day C-P, Pan Y, Nakajima Y, Hung M-C 2006. Co-regulation of B-Myb expression by E2F1 and EGF receptor. *Molecular Carcinogenesis* 45:10–17. DOI: 10.1002/mc.20147.
- Hanzlikova H, Kalasova I, Demin AA, Pennicott LE, Cihlarova Z, Caldecott KW 2018. The Importance of Poly(ADP-Ribose) Polymerase as a Sensor of Unligated Okazaki Fragments during DNA Replication. *Molecular cell* 71:319–331.e3. DOI: 10.1016/j.molcel.2018.06.004.
- Hao B, Oehlmann S, Sowa ME, Harper JW, Pavletich NP 2007. Structure of a Fbw7-Skp1-Cyclin E Complex: Multisite-Phosphorylated Substrate Recognition by SCF Ubiquitin Ligases. *Molecular cell* 26:131–143. DOI: 10.1016/j.molcel.2007.02.022.
- Hatch EM, Kulukian A, Holland AJ, Cleveland DW, Stearns T 2010. Cep152 interacts with Plk4 and is required for centriole duplication. *J Cell Biol* 191:721–729. DOI: 10.1083/jcb.201006049.
- Hemerly AS, Prasanth SG, Siddiqui K, Stillman B 2009. Orc1 controls centriole and centrosome copy number in human cells. *Science* 323:789–793. DOI: 10.1126/science.1166745.
- Hilbert M, Noga A, Frey D, Hamel V, Guichard P, Kraatz SHW, Pfreundschuh M, Hosner S, Flückiger I, Jaussi R, Wieser MM, Thieltes KM, Deupi X, Müller DJ, Kammerer RA, Gönczy P, Hirono M, Steinmetz MO 2016. SAS-6 engineering reveals interdependence between cartwheel and microtubules in determining centriole architecture. *Nature Cell Biology* 18:393–403. DOI: 10.1038/ncb3329.
- Hiraga S-I, Alvino GM, Chang F, Lian H-Y, Sridhar A, Kubota T, Brewer BJ, Weinreich M, Raghuraman MK, Donaldson AD 2014. Rif1 controls DNA replication by directing Protein Phosphatase 1 to reverse Cdc7-mediated phosphorylation of the MCM complex. *Genes & Development* 28:372–383. DOI: 10.1101/gad.231258.113.
- Hizume K, Endo S, Muramatsu S, Kobayashi T, Araki H 2018. DNA polymerase ϵ -dependent modulation of the pausing property of the CMG helicase at the barrier. *Genes & Development* 32:1315–1320. DOI: 10.1101/gad.317073.118.
- Honaker Y, Piwnicka-Worms H 2010. Casein kinase 1 functions as both penultimate and ultimate kinase in regulating Cdc25A destruction. *Oncogene* 29:3324–3334. DOI: 10.1038/onc.2010.96.
- Honda R, Lowe ED, Dubinina E, Skamnaki V, Cook A, Brown NR, Johnson LN 2005. The structure of cyclin E1/CDK2: implications for CDK2 activation and CDK2-independent roles. *The EMBO Journal* 24:452–463. DOI: 10.1038/sj.emboj.7600554.
- Hossain M, Stillman B 2016. Opposing roles for DNA replication initiator proteins ORC1 and CDC6 in control of Cyclin E gene transcription. *eLife* 5:4294. DOI: 10.7554/eLife.12785.
- Hsieh J-K, Yap D, O'Connor DJ, Fogal V, Fallis L, Chan F, Zhong S, Lu X 2002. Novel function of the cyclin A binding site of E2F in regulating p53-induced apoptosis in response to DNA damage. *Molecular and cellular biology* 22:78–93. DOI: 10.1128/mcb.22.1.78-93.2002.
- Hu S, Danilov AV, Godek K, Orr B, Tafe LJ, Rodriguez-Canales J, Behrens C, Mino B, Moran CA, Memoli VA, Mustachio LM, Galimberti F, Ravi S, DeCastro A, Lu Y, Sekula D, Andrew AS, Wistuba II, Freemantle S, Compton DA, Dmitrovsky E 2015a. CDK2 Inhibition Causes Anaphase Catastrophe in Lung Cancer through the Centrosomal Protein CP110. *Cancer Res* 75:2029–2038. DOI: 10.1158/0008-5472.CAN-14-1494.
- Hu S, Lu Y, Orr B, Godek K, Mustachio LM, Kawakami M, Sekula D, Compton DA, Freemantle S, Dmitrovsky E 2015b. Specific CP110

- Phosphorylation Sites Mediate Anaphase Catastrophe after CDK2 Inhibition: Evidence for Cooperation with USP33 Knockdown. *Mol Cancer Ther* 14:2576.
- Hughes BT, Sidorova J, Swanger J, Monnat RJ, Clurman BE 2013. Essential role for Cdk2 inhibitory phosphorylation during replication stress revealed by a human Cdk2 knockin mutation. *Proc Natl Acad Sci USA* 110:8954–8959. DOI: 10.1073/pnas.1302927110.
- Ivanova IA, Nakrieko K-A, Dagnino L 2009. Phosphorylation by p38 MAP kinase is required for E2F1 degradation and keratinocyte differentiation. *Oncogene* 28:52–62. DOI: 10.1038/onc.2008.354.
- Jeffrey PD, Russo AA, Polyak K, Gibbs E, Hurwitz J, Massagué J, Pavletich NP 1995. Mechanism of CDK activation revealed by the structure of a cyclinA-CDK2 complex. *Nature* 376:313–320. DOI: 10.1038/376313a0.
- Jeffrey PD, Tong L, Pavletich NP 2000. Structural basis of inhibition of CDK-cyclin complexes by INK4 inhibitors. *Genes & Development* 14:3115–3125.
- Jensen, L., Jensen, T., de Lichtenberg, U., Brunak, S., and Bork, P. (2006). Co-evolution of transcriptional and post-translational cell-cycle regulation. *Nature* 443, 594.
- Jin J, Shirogane T, Xu L, Nalepa G, Qin J, Elledge SJ, Harper JW 2003. SCFbeta-TRCP links Chk1 signaling to degradation of the Cdc25A protein phosphatase. *Genes & Development* 17:3062–3074.
- Joaquin M, Watson RJ 2003. Cell cycle regulation by the B-Myb transcription factor. *Cellular and Molecular Life Sciences CMLS* 60:2389–2401.
- Kanakkanthara A, Jeganathan KB, Limzerwala JF, Baker DJ, Hamada M, Nam H-J, van Deursen WH, Hamada N, Naylor RM, Becker NA, Davies BA, van Ree JH, Mer G, Shapiro VS, Maher LJ, Katzmann DJ, van Deursen JM 2016. Cyclin A2 is an RNA binding protein that controls Mre11 mRNA translation. *Science* 353:1549.
- Kang S, Kang M-S, Ryu E, Myung K 2018. Eukaryotic DNA replication: Orchestrated action of multi-subunit protein complexes. *Mutation research* 809:58–69. DOI: 10.1016/j.mrfmmm.2017.04.002.
- Kang S, Warner MD, Bell SP 2014. Multiple Functions for Mcm2–7 ATPase Motifs during Replication Initiation. *Molecular cell* 55:655–665. DOI: 10.1016/j.molcel.2014.06.033.
- Kang T, Wei Y, Honaker Y, Yamaguchi H, Appella E, Hung M-C, Piwnicka-Worms H 2008. GSK-3 β Targets Cdc25A for Ubiquitin-Mediated Proteolysis, and GSK-3 β Inactivation Correlates with Cdc25A Overproduction in Human Cancers. *Cancer Cell* 13:36–47.
- Kanie T, Onoyama I, Matsumoto A, Yamada M, Nakatsumi H, Tateishi Y, Yamamura S, Tsunematsu R, Matsumoto M, Nakayama KI 2012. Genetic reevaluation of the role of F-box proteins in cyclin D1 degradation. *Molecular and cellular biology* 32:590–605. DOI: 10.1128/MCB.06570-11.
- Kasahara K, Goto H, Enomoto M, Tomono Y, Kiyono T, Inagaki M 2010. 14-3-3gamma mediates Cdc25A proteolysis to block premature mitotic entry after DNA damage. *The EMBO Journal* 29:2802–2812. DOI: 10.1038/emboj.2010.157.
- Katsuno Y, Suzuki A, Sugimura K, Okumura K, Zineldeen DH, Shimada M, Niida H, Mizuno T, Hanaoka F, Nakanishi M 2009. Cyclin A-Cdk1 regulates the origin firing program in mammalian cells. *Proc Natl Acad Sci USA* 106:3184–3189. DOI: 10.1073/pnas.0809350106.
- Katz M, Amit I, Yarden Y 2007. Regulation of MAPKs by growth factors and receptor tyrosine kinases. *Mitogen-Activated Protein Kinases: New Insights on Regulation, Function and Role in Human Disease* 1773:1161–1176.
- Kim G-Y, Mercer SE, Ewton DZ, Yan Z, Jin K, Friedman E 2002. The stress-activated protein kinases p38 alpha and JNK1 stabilize p21(Cip1) by phosphorylation. *The Journal of biological chemistry* 277:29792–29802. DOI: 10.1074/jbc.M201299200.
- Klebba JE, Buster DW, McLamarrh TA, Rusan NM, Rogers GC 2015. Autoinhibition and relief mechanism for Polo-like kinase 4. *Proc Natl Acad Sci USA* 112:E657–66. DOI: 10.1073/pnas.1417967112.
- Kliszczak M, Sedlackova H, Pitchai GP, Streicher WW, Krejci L, Hickson ID 2015. Interaction of RECQ4 and MCM10 is important for efficient DNA replication origin firing in human cells. *Oncotarget* 6:40464–40479. DOI: 10.18632/oncotarget.6342.
- Knudsen KE, Diehl JA, Haiman CA, Knudsen ES 2006. Cyclin D1: polymorphism, aberrant splicing and cancer risk. *Oncogene* 25:1620–1628. DOI: 10.1038/sj.onc.1209371.
- Kodani A, Moyer T, Chen A, Holland A, Walsh CA, Reiter JF 2019. SFI1 promotes centriole duplication by recruiting USP9X to stabilize the microcephaly protein STIL. *J Cell Biol*. 218(7):2185–2197.
- Kose HB, Larsen NB, Duxin JP, Yardimci H 2019. Dynamics of the Eukaryotic Replicative Helicase at Lagging-Strand Protein Barriers Support the Steric Exclusion Model. *Cell reports* 26:2113–2125.e6.
- Kraatz S, Guichard P, Obbineni JM, Olieric N, Hatzopoulos GN, Hilbert M, Sen I, Missimer J, Gönczy P, Steinmetz MO 2016. The Human Centriolar Protein CEP135 Contains a Two-Stranded Coiled-Coil Domain Critical for Microtubule Binding. *Structure* 24:1358–1371.
- Kratz A-S, Bärenz F, Richter KT, Hoffmann I 2015. Plk4-dependent phosphorylation of STIL is required for centriole duplication. *Biology Open* 4:370–377. DOI: 10.1242/bio.201411023.
- Kreis N-N, Friemel A, Zimmer B, Roth S, Rieger MA, Rolle U, Louwen F, Yuan J 2016. Mitotic p21 Cip1/CDKN1A is regulated by cyclin-dependent kinase 1 phosphorylation. *Oncotarget* 7:50215–50228. DOI: 10.18632/oncotarget.10330.
- Krek W, Xu G, Livingston DM 1995. Cyclin A-kinase regulation of E2F-1 DNA binding function underlies suppression of an S phase checkpoint. *Cell* 83:1149–1158. DOI: 10.1016/0092-8674(95)90141-8.
- Kumagai A, Lee J, Yoo HY, Dunphy WG 2006. TopBP1 Activates the ATR-ATRIP Complex. *Cell* 124:943–955. DOI: 10.1016/j.cell.2005.12.041.
- Kumagai A, Shevchenko A, Shevchenko A, Dunphy WG 2010. Treslin Collaborates with TopBP1 in Triggering the Initiation of DNA Replication. *Cell* 140:349–359. DOI: 10.1016/j.cell.2009.12.049.
- Kumagai A, Shevchenko A, Shevchenko A, Dunphy WG 2011. Direct regulation of Treslin by cyclin-dependent kinase is essential for the onset of DNA replication. *J Cell Biol* 193:995–1007. DOI: 10.1083/jcb.201102003.
- Langston LD, Mayle R, Schauer GD, Yurieva O, Zhang D, Yao NY, Georgescu RE, O'Donnell ME 2017. Mcm10 promotes rapid isomerization of CMG-DNA for replisome bypass of lagging strand DNA blocks. *eLife* 6:465. DOI: 10.7554/eLife.29118.
- Langston LD, Zhang D, Yurieva O, Georgescu RE, Finkelstein J, Yao NY, Indiani C, O'Donnell ME 2014. CMG helicase and DNA polymerase ϵ form a functional 15-subunit holoenzyme for eukaryotic leading-strand DNA replication. *Proc Natl Acad Sci USA* 111:15390–15395. DOI: 10.1073/pnas.1418334111.
- Larasati, Duncker B 2017. Mechanisms Governing DDK Regulation of the Initiation of DNA Replication. *Genes* 8:3–12. DOI: 10.3390/genes8010003.
- Larrea MD, Liang J, Da Silva T, Hong F, Shao SH, Han K, Dumont D, Slingerland JM 2008. Phosphorylation of p27Kip1 regulates assembly and activation of cyclin D1-Cdk4. *Molecular and cellular biology* 28:6462–6472. DOI: 10.1128/MCB.02300-07.
- Lauper N, Beck AR, Cariou S, Richman L, Hofmann K, Reith W, Slingerland JM, Amati B 1998. Cyclin E2: a novel CDK2 partner in the late G1 and S phases of the mammalian cell cycle. *Oncogene* 17:2637–2643. DOI: 10.1038/sj.onc.1202477.
- Lee C, Hong B, Choi JM, Kim Y, Watanabe S, Ishimi Y, Enomoto T, Tada S, Kim Y, Cho Y 2004. Structural basis for inhibition of the replication licensing factor Cdt1 by geminin. *Nature* 430:913–917. DOI: 10.1038/nature02813.
- Lee KY, Bae JS, Yoon S, Hwang DS 2014. Dephosphorylation of Orc2 by protein phosphatase 1 promotes the binding of the origin recognition complex to chromatin. *Biochemical and biophysical research communications* 448:385–389.
- Lee KY, Bang SW, Yoon SW, Lee S-H, Yoon J-B, Hwang DS 2012. Phosphorylation of ORC2 Protein Dissociates Origin Recognition Complex from Chromatin and Replication Origins. *Journal of Biological Chemistry* 287:11891–11898.
- Lee M, Seo MY, Chang J, Hwang DS, Rhee K 2017. PLK4 phosphorylation of CP110 is required for efficient centriole assembly. *Cell Cycle* 16:1225–1234. DOI: 10.1080/15384101.2017.1325555.
- Lemmens B, Hégarat N, Akopyan K, Sala-Gaston J, Bartek J, Hochegger H, Lindqvist A 2018. DNA Replication Determines Timing of Mitosis by Restricting CDK1 and PLK1 Activation. *Molecular cell* 71:117–128.e3. DOI: 10.1016/j.molcel.2018.05.026.

- Lents NH, Keenan SM, Bellone C, Baldassare JJ 2002. Stimulation of the Raf/MEK/ERK cascade is necessary and sufficient for activation and Thr-160 phosphorylation of a nuclear-targeted CDK2. *The Journal of biological chemistry* 277:47469–47475. DOI: 10.1074/jbc.M207425200.
- Li H, O'Donnell ME 2018. The Eukaryotic CMG Helicase at the Replication Fork: Emerging Architecture Reveals an Unexpected Mechanism. *BioEssays : news and reviews in molecular, cellular and developmental biology* 40:1700208. DOI: 10.1002/bies.201700208.
- Li J, D'Angiolella V, Seeley ES, Kim S, Kobayashi T, Fu W, Campos El, Pagano M, Dynlacht BD 2013. USP33 regulates centrosome biogenesis via deubiquitination of the centriolar protein CP110. *Nature* 495:255–259. DOI: 10.1038/nature11941.
- Li P, Goto H, Kasahara K, Matsuyama M, Wang Z, Yatabe Y, Kiyono T, Inagaki M 2012. P90 RSK arranges Chk1 in the nucleus for monitoring of genomic integrity during cell proliferation. *MBoC* 23:1582–1592. DOI: 10.1091/mbc.e11-10-0883.
- Liang J, Slingerland JM 2003. Multiple roles of the PI3K/PKB (Akt) pathway in cell cycle progression. *Cell Cycle* 2:339–345.
- Lin YC, Chang CW, Hsu W-B, Tang C-J, Lin YN, Chou E-J, Wu CT, Tang TK 2013. Human microcephaly protein CEP135 binds to hSAS-6 and CPAP, and is required for centriole assembly. *The EMBO Journal* 32:1141–1154. DOI: 10.1038/emboj.2013.56.
- Ling Zheng L, Wang FY, Cong XX, Shen Y, Rao XS, Huang DS, Fan W, Yi P, Wang XB, Zheng L, Zhou YT, Luo Y 2015. Interaction of Heat Shock Protein Cpn10 with the Cyclin E/Cdk2 Substrate Nuclear Protein Ataxia-Telangiectasia (NPAT) Is Involved in Regulating Histone Transcription. *The Journal of biological chemistry* 290:29290–29300. DOI: 10.1074/jbc.M115.659201.
- Liu E, Li X, Yan F, Zhao Q, Wu X 2004. Cyclin-dependent kinases phosphorylate human Cdt1 and induce its degradation. *The Journal of biological chemistry* 279:17283–17288. DOI: 10.1074/jbc.C300549200.
- Liu S, Bekker-Jensen S, Mailand N, Lukas C, Bartek J, Lukas J 2006. Claspin operates downstream of TopBP1 to direct ATR signaling towards Chk1 activation. *Molecular and cellular biology* 26:6056–6064. DOI: 10.1128/MCB.00492-06.
- Liu S, Shiotani B, Lahiri M, Maréchal A, Tse A, Leung CCY, Glover JNM, Yang XH, Zou L 2011. ATR Autophosphorylation as a Molecular Switch for Checkpoint Activation. *Molecular cell* 43:192–202. DOI: 10.1016/j.molcel.2011.06.019.
- Liu S, Xu Z, Leng H, Zheng P, Yang J, Chen K, Feng J, Li Q 2017. RPA binds histone H3-H4 and functions in DNA replication-coupled nucleosome assembly. *Science* 355:415–420. DOI: 10.1126/science.aah4712.
- Liu Y, Gupta GD, Barnabas DD, Agircan FG, Mehmood S, Di Wu, Coyaud E, Johnson CM, McLaughlin SH, Andreeva A, Freund SMV, Robinson CV, Cheung SWT, Raught B, Pelletier L, van Breugel M 2018. Direct binding of CEP85 to STIL ensures robust PLK4 activation and efficient centriole assembly. *Nat Commun* 9:1731. DOI: 10.1038/s41467-018-04122-x.
- Liu Y, Wu C, Galaktionov K 2004. p42, a novel cyclin-dependent kinase-activating kinase in mammalian cells. *The Journal of biological chemistry* 279:4507–4514. DOI: 10.1074/jbc.M309995200.
- Lozano J-C, Perret E, Schatt P, Arnould C, Peaucellier G, Picard A 2002. Molecular Cloning, Gene Localization, and Structure of Human Cyclin B3. *Biochemical and biophysical research communications* 291:406–413. DOI: 10.1006/bbrc.2002.6458.
- Löoke M, Maloney MF, Bell SP 2017. Mcm10 regulates DNA replication elongation by stimulating the CMG replicative helicase. *Genes & Development* 31:291–305.
- Lu F, Lan R, Zhang H, Jiang Q, Zhang C 2009. Geminin is partially localized to the centrosome and plays a role in proper centrosome duplication. *Biology of the Cell* 101:273–285. DOI: 10.1042/BC20080109.
- Lujan SA, Williams JS, Kunkel TA 2016. DNA Polymerases Divide the Labor of Genome Replication. *Trends in cell biology* 26:640–654.
- Lutzmann M, Maiorano D, Méchali M 2006. A Cdt1-geminin complex licenses chromatin for DNA replication and prevents rereplication during S phase in Xenopus. *The EMBO Journal* 25:5764–5774. DOI: 10.1038/sj.emboj.7601436.
- Ma T, Van Tine BA, Wei Y, Garrett MD, Nelson D, Adams PD, Wang J, Qin J, Chow LT, Harper JW 2000. Cell cycle-regulated phosphorylation of p220(NPAT) by cyclin E/Cdk2 in Cajal bodies promotes histone gene transcription. *Genes & Development* 14:2298–2313. DOI: 10.1101/gad.829500.
- Ma, D.K., C. Stolte, S. Kaur, M. Bain, and S.I. O'Donoghue. 2013. Visual analytics of phosphorylation time-series data on insulin response. AIP Conference Proceedings. 1559:185–196. doi:10.1063/1.4825010 .
- Ma, D.K., C. Stolte, J.R. Krycer, D.E. James, and S.I. O'Donoghue. 2015. SnapShot: Insulin/IGF1 Signaling. *Cell*. 161:948 948.e1. doi:10.1016/j.cell.2015.04.041 .
- Mazars A, Fernandez-Vidal A, Mondesert O, Lorenzo C, Prévost G, Ducommun B, Payrastré B, Racaud-Sultan C, Manenti S 2009. A caspase-dependent cleavage of CDC25A generates an active fragment activating cyclin-dependent kinase 2 during apoptosis. *Cell Death Differ* 16:208–218. DOI: 10.1038/cdd.2008.142.
- McCubrey JA, Steelman LS, Chappell WH, Abrams SL, Wong EWT, Chang F, Lehmann B, Terrian DM, Milella M, Tafuri A, Stivala F, Libra M, Basecke J, Evangelisti C, Martelli AM, Franklin RA 2007. Roles of the Raf/MEK/ERK pathway in cell growth, malignant transformation and drug resistance. *Mitogen-Activated Protein Kinases: New Insights on Regulation, Function and Role in Human Disease* 1773:1263–1284. DOI: 10.1016/j.bbamcr.2006.10.001.
- McGowan CH, Russell P 1993. Human Wee1 kinase inhibits cell division by phosphorylating p34cdc2 exclusively on Tyr15. *The EMBO Journal* 12:75–85.
- McLamarrah TA, Buster DW, Galletta BJ, Boese CJ, Ryniawec JM, Hollingsworth NA, Byrnes AE, Brownlee CW, Slep KC, Rusan NM, Rogers GC 2018. An ordered pattern of Ana2 phosphorylation by Plk4 is required for centriole assembly. *J Cell Biol* 217:1217–1231. DOI: 10.1083/jcb.201605106.
- Melixietan M, Klein DK, Sørensen CS, Helin K 2009. NEK11 regulates CDC25A degradation and the IR-induced G2/M checkpoint. *Nature Cell Biology* 11:1247–1253. DOI: 10.1038/ncb1969.
- Méndez J, Zou-Yang XH, Kim S-Y, Hidaka M, Tansey WP, Stillman B 2002. Human Origin Recognition Complex Large Subunit Is Degraded by Ubiquitin-Mediated Proteolysis after Initiation of DNA Replication. *Molecular cell* 9:481–491. DOI: 10.1016/S1097-2765(02)00467-7.
- Miyazawa Onami M, Araki H, Tanaka S 2017. Pre-initiation complex assembly functions as a molecular switch that splits the Mcm2-7 double hexamer. *EMBO reports* 18:1752–1761. DOI: 10.15252/embr.201744206.
- Mo D, Zhao Y, Balajee AS 2018. Human RecQL4 helicase plays multifaceted roles in the genomic stability of normal and cancer cells. *Cancer letters* 413:1–10. DOI: 10.1016/j.canlet.2017.10.021.
- Moiseeva TN, Bakkenist CJ 2018. Regulation of the initiation of DNA replication in human cells. *DNA repair* 72:99–106. DOI: 10.1016/j.dnarep.2018.09.003.
- Moiseeva TN, Yin Y, Calderon MJ, Qian C, Schamus-Haynes S, Sugitani N, Osmanbeyoglu HU, Rothenberg E, Watkins SC, Bakkenist CJ 2019. An ATR and CHK1 kinase signaling mechanism that limits origin firing during unperturbed DNA replication. *Proc Natl Acad Sci USA*. 116(27):13374–13383. doi: 10.1073/pnas.1903418116
- Moser J, Miller I, Carter D, Spencer SL 2018. Control of the Restriction Point by Rb and p21. *Proc Natl Acad Sci USA* 115:E8219–E8227. DOI: 10.1073/pnas.1722446115.
- Moyer TC, Clutario KM, Lambrus BG, Daggubati V, Holland AJ 2015. Binding of STIL to Plk4 activates kinase activity to promote centriole assembly. *J Cell Biol* 209:863.
- Mu R, Tat J, Zamudio R, Zhang Y, Yates JR, Kumagai A, Dunphy WG, Reed SI 2017. CKS Proteins Promote Checkpoint Recovery by Stimulating Phosphorylation of Treslin. *Molecular and cellular biology* 37:e00344–17. DOI: 10.1128/MCB.00344-17.
- Müller-Tidow C, Wang W, Idos GE, Diederichs S, Yang R, Readhead C, Berdel WE, Serve H, Saville M, Watson R, Koeffler HP 2001. Cyclin A1 directly interacts with B-myb and cyclin A1/cdk2 phosphorylate B-myb at functionally important serine and threonine residues: tissue-specific regulation of B-myb function. *Blood* 97:2091–2097. DOI: 10.1182/blood.V97.7.2091.
- Nam H-J, van Deursen JM 2014. Cyclin B2 and p53 control proper timing of centrosome separation. *Nature Cell Biology* 16:535–546. DOI: 10.1038/ncb2952.
- Narasimha AM, Kaulich M, Shapiro GS, Choi YJ, Sicinski P, Dowdy SF 2014. Cyclin D activates the Rb tumor suppressor by mono-phosphorylation. *eLife* 3:1068. DOI: 10.7554/eLife.02872.

- Niehrs C, Acebron SP 2012. Mitotic and mitogenic Wnt signalling. *The EMBO Journal* 31:2705–2713. DOI: 10.1038/emboj.2012.124.
- O'Donoghue SI, Sabir KS, Kalemanov M, Stolte C, Wellmann B, Ho V, Roos M, Perdigão N, Buske FA, Heinrich J, Rost B, Schaffnerhans A 2015. Aquaria: simplifying discovery and insight from protein structures. *Nature Methods*. Feb;12(2):98-9. doi: 10.1038/nmeth.3258.
- Oakes V, Wang W, Harrington B, Lee WJ, Beamish H, Chia KM, Pinder A, Goto H, Inagaki M, Pavey S, Gabrielli B 2014. Cyclin A/Cdk2 regulates Cdh1 and claspin during late S/G2 phase of the cell cycle. *Cell Cycle* 13:3302–3311. DOI: 10.4161/15384101.2014.949111.
- Ohta M, Watanabe K, Ashikawa T, Nozaki Y, Yoshida S, Kimura A, Kitagawa D 2018. Bimodal Binding of STIL to Plk4 Controls Proper Centriole Copy Number. *Cell reports* 23:3160–3169.e4. DOI: 10.1016/j.celrep.2018.05.030.
- Ohtani K, DeGregori J, Nevins JR 1995. Regulation of the cyclin E gene by transcription factor E2F1. *Proc Natl Acad Sci USA* 92:12146–12150. DOI: 10.1073/pnas.92.26.12146.
- Onesti S, MacNeill SA 2013. Structure and evolutionary origins of the CMG complex. *Chromosoma* 122:47–53. DOI: 10.1007/s00412-013-0397-x.
- Ou L, Ferreira AM, Otieno S, Xiao L, Bashford D, Kriwacki RW 2011. Incomplete folding upon binding mediates Cdk4/cyclin D complex activation by tyrosine phosphorylation of inhibitor p27 protein. *The Journal of biological chemistry* 286:30142–30151. DOI: 10.1074/jbc.M111.244095.
- Parker MW, Botchan MR, Berger JM 2017. Mechanisms and regulation of DNA replication initiation in eukaryotes. *Critical Reviews in Biochemistry and Molecular Biology* 52:107–144. DOI: 10.1080/10409238.2016.1274717.
- Patel P, Asbach B, Shteyn E, Gomez C, Coltoff A, Bhuyan S, Tyner AL, Wagner R, Blain SW 2015. Brk/Protein tyrosine kinase 6 phosphorylates p27KIP1, regulating the activity of cyclin D-cyclin-dependent kinase 4. *Molecular and cellular biology* 35:1506–1522. DOI: 10.1128/MCB.01206-14.
- Pellegrini L 2012. The Pol α -Primase Complex. In: *The Eukaryotic Replisome: a Guide to Protein Structure and Function*. Subcellular Biochemistry. Dordrecht: Springer Netherlands, 157–169. DOI: 10.1007/978-94-007-4572-8_9.
- Pellegrini L, Costa A 2016. New Insights into the Mechanism of DNA Duplication by the Eukaryotic Replisome. *Trends in biochemical sciences* 41:859–871.
- Perez-Arnaiz P, Bruck I, Colbert MK, Kaplan DL 2017. An intact Mcm10 coiled-coil interaction surface is important for origin melting, helicase assembly and the recruitment of Pol- α to Mcm2–7. *Nucleic acids research* 45:7261–7275.
- Petermann E, Woodcock M, Helleday T 2010. Chk1 promotes replication fork progression by controlling replication initiation. *Proc Natl Acad Sci USA* 107:16090–16095. DOI: 10.1073/pnas.1005031107.
- Petersen BO, Lukas J, Sørensen CS, Bartek J, Helin K 1999. Phosphorylation of mammalian CDC6 by cyclin A/CDK2 regulates its subcellular localization. *The EMBO Journal* 18:396–410. DOI: 10.1093/emboj/18.2.396.
- Petryk N, Dalby M, Wenger A, Stromme CB, Strandsby A, Andersson R, Groth A 2018. MCM2 promotes symmetric inheritance of modified histones during DNA replication. *Science* 361:1389–1392. DOI: 10.1126/science.aau0294.
- Pilkinton M, Sandoval R, Song J, Ness SA, Colamonici OR 2007. Mip/LIN-9 regulates the expression of B-Myb and the induction of cyclin A, cyclin B, and CDK1. *The Journal of biological chemistry* 282:168–175. DOI: 10.1074/jbc.M609924200.
- Porter AC, Vaillancourt RR 1998. Tyrosine kinase receptor-activated signal transduction pathways which lead to oncogenesis. *Oncogene* 17:1343–1352. DOI: 10.1038/sj.onc.1202171.
- Pozo P, Cook J 2017. Regulation and Function of Cdt1; A Key Factor in Cell Proliferation and Genome Stability. *Genes* 8:2–23. DOI: 10.3390/genes8010002.
- Puklowski A, Homsy Y, Keller D, May M, Chauhan S, Kossatz U, Grünwald V, Kubicka S, Pich A, Manns MP, Hoffmann I, Gönczy P, Malek NP 2011. The SCF–FBXW5 E3-ubiquitin ligase is regulated by PLK4 and targets HsSAS-6 to control centrosome duplication. *Nature Cell Biology* 13:1004–1009. DOI: 10.1038/ncb2282.
- Rao Q, Liu M, Tian Y, Wu Z, Hao Y, Song L, Qin Z, Ding C, Wang H-W, Wang J, Xu Y 2018. Cryo-EM structure of human ATR-ATRIP complex. *Cell Research* 28:143–156.
- Ray A, James MK, Larochelle S, Fisher RP, Blain SW 2009. p27Kip1 inhibits cyclin D-cyclin-dependent kinase 4 by two independent modes. *Molecular and cellular biology* 29:986–999. DOI: 10.1128/MCB.00898-08.
- Remus D, Beuron F, Tolun G, Griffith JD, Morris EP, Diffley JFX 2009. Concerted Loading of Mcm2–7 Double Hexamers around DNA during DNA Replication Origin Licensing. *Cell* 139:719–730. DOI: 10.1016/j.cell.2009.10.015.
- Rickman K, Smogorzewska A 2019. Advances in understanding DNA processing and protection at stalled replication forks. *J Cell Biol* 218:1096–1107. DOI: 10.1083/jcb.201809012.
- Rogers S, Gloss BS, Lee CS, Sergio CM, Dinger ME, Musgrove EA, Burgess A, Caldon CE 2015. Cyclin E2 is the predominant E-cyclin associated with NPAT in breast cancer cells. *Cell Division* 10:1. DOI: 10.1186/s13008-015-0007-9.
- Rubin SM 2013. Deciphering the retinoblastoma protein phosphorylation code. *Trends in biochemical sciences* 38:12–19.
- Russo AA, Tong L, Lee J-O, Jeffrey PD, Pavletich NP 1998. Structural basis for inhibition of the cyclin-dependent kinase Cdk6 by the tumour suppressor p16 INK4a. *Nature* 395:237–243. DOI: 10.1038/26155.
- Sadasivam S, Duan S, DeCaprio JA 2012. The MuvB complex sequentially recruits B-Myb and FoxM1 to promote mitotic gene expression. *Genes & Development* 26:474–489. DOI: 10.1101/gad.181933.111.
- Saldivar JC, Cortez D, Cimprich KA 2017. The essential kinase ATR: ensuring faithful duplication of a challenging genome. *Nature reviews. Molecular cell biology* 18:622–636. DOI: 10.1038/nrm.2017.67.
- Saldivar JC, Hamperl S, Bocek MJ, Chung M, Bass TE, Cisneros-Soberanis F, Samejima K, Xie L, Paulson JR, Earnshaw WC, Cortez D, Meyer T, Cimprich KA 2018. An intrinsic S/G2checkpoint enforced by ATR. *Science* 361:806–810. DOI: 10.1126/science.aap9346.
- Sansam CG, Goins D, Siefert JC, Clowdus EA, Sansam CL 2015. Cyclin-dependent kinase regulates the length of S phase through TICRR/TRESLIN phosphorylation. *Genes & Development* 29:555–566.
- Schachter MM, Merrick KA, Larochelle S, Hirschi A, Zhang C, Shokat KM, Rubin SM, Fisher RP 2013. A Cdk7-Cdk4 T-Loop Phosphorylation Cascade Promotes G1 Progression. *Molecular cell* 50:250–260.
- Schmidt TI, Kleylein-Sohn J, Westendorf J, Le Clech M, Lavoie SB, Stierhof Y-D, Nigg EA 2009. Control of Centriole Length by CPAP and CP110. *Current Biology* 19:1005–1011.
- Schmitt E, Boutros R, Froment C, Monsarrat B, Ducommun B, Dozier C 2006. CHK1 phosphorylates CDC25B during the cell cycle in the absence of DNA damage. *Journal of cell science* 119:4269–4275. DOI: 10.1242/jcs.03200.
- Schwarz C, Johnson A, Köivomägi M, Zatulovskiy E, Kravitz CJ, Donic A, Skotheim JM 2018. A Precise Cdk Activity Threshold Determines Passage through the Restriction Point. *Molecular cell* 69:253–264.e5. DOI: 10.1016/j.molcel.2017.12.017.
- Sears R, Nuckolls F, Haura E, Taya Y, Tamai K, Nevins JR 2000. Multiple Ras-dependent phosphorylation pathways regulate Myc protein stability. *Genes & Development* 14:2501–2514. DOI: 10.1101/gad.836800.
- Seo HR, Kim J, Bae S, Soh J-W, Lee Y-S 2008. Cdk5-mediated phosphorylation of c-Myc on Ser-62 is essential in transcriptional activation of cyclin B1 by cyclin G1. *The Journal of biological chemistry* 283:15601–15610. DOI: 10.1074/jbc.M800987200.
- Seo Y-S, Kang Y-H 2018. The Human Replicative Helicase, the CMG Complex, as a Target for Anti-cancer Therapy. *Frontiers in Molecular Biosciences* 5:26. DOI: 10.3389/fmolb.2018.00026.
- Serrano M, Hannon GJ, Beach D 1993. A new regulatory motif in cell-cycle control causing specific inhibition of cyclin D/CDK4. *Nature* 366:704–707. DOI: 10.1038/366704a0.
- Sheu Y-J, Stillman B 2010. The Dbf4–Cdc7 kinase promotes S phase by alleviating an inhibitory activity in Mcm4. *Nature* 463:113–117. DOI: 10.1038/nature08647.
- Shiromizu T, Goto H, Tomono Y, Bartek J, Totsukawa G, Inoko A, Nakanishi M, Matsumura F, Inagaki M 2006. Regulation of mitotic function of Chk1 through phosphorylation at novel sites by cyclin-

- dependent kinase 1 (Cdk1). *Genes to Cells* 11:477–485. DOI: 10.1111/j.1365-2443.2006.00955.x.
- Smits VAJ, Cabrera E, Freire R, Gillespie DA 2019. Claspin – checkpoint adaptor and DNA replication factor. *The FEBS Journal* 286:441–455. DOI: 10.1111/febs.14594.
- Sokka M, Koalick D, Hemmerich P, Syväoja J, Pospiech H 2018. The ATR-Activation Domain of TopBP1 Is Required for the Suppression of Origin Firing during the S Phase. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences* 19:2376–15. DOI: 10.3390/ijms19082376.
- Sotiriou SK, Kamileri I, Lugli N, Evangelou K, Da-Ré C, Huber F, Padayachy L, Tardy S, Nicati NL, Barriot S, Ochs F, Lukas C, Lukas J, Gorgoulis VG, Scapozza L, Halazonetis TD 2016. Mammalian RAD52 Functions in Break-Induced Replication Repair of Collapsed DNA Replication Forks. *Molecular cell* 64:1127–1134. DOI: 10.1016/j.molcel.2016.10.038.
- Sparks JL, Chistol G, Gao AO, Räschele M, Larsen NB, Mann M, Duxin JP, Walter JC 2019. The CMG Helicase Bypasses DNA-Protein Cross-Links to Facilitate Their Repair. *Cell* 176:167–181.e21. DOI: 10.1016/j.cell.2018.10.053.
- Spies J, Lukas C, Somyajit K, Rask M-B, Lukas J, Neelsen KJ 2019. 53BP1 nuclear bodies enforce replication timing at under-replicated DNA to limit heritable DNA damage. *Nature Cell Biology* 21:487–497. DOI: 10.1038/s41556-019-0293-6.
- Stodola JL, Burgers PM 2016. Resolving individual steps of Okazaki-fragment maturation at a millisecond timescale. *Nature Structural & Molecular Biology* 23:402–408. DOI: 10.1038/nsmb.3207.
- Stodola JL, Burgers PM 2018. Mechanism of Lagging-Strand DNA Replication in Eukaryotes. In: *DNA Replication. Advances in Experimental Medicine and Biology*. Singapore: Springer Singapore, 117–133. DOI: 10.1007/978-981-10-6955-0_6.
- Sugimoto N, Tatsumi Y, Tsurumi T, Matsukage A, Kiyono T, Nishitani H, Fujita M 2004. Cdt1 phosphorylation by cyclin A-dependent kinases negatively regulates its function without affecting geminin binding. *The Journal of biological chemistry* 279:19691–19697. DOI: 10.1074/jbc.M313175200.
- Sun J, Fernández-Cid A, Riera A, Tognetti S, Yuan Z, Stillman B, Speck C, Li H 2014. Structural and mechanistic insights into Mcm2-7 double-hexamer assembly and function. *Genes & Development* 28:2291–2303. DOI: 10.1101/gad.242313.114.
- Swanson C, Ross J, Jackson PK 2000. Nuclear accumulation of cyclin E/Cdk2 triggers a concentration-dependent switch for the destruction of p27^{Xic1}. *Proc Natl Acad Sci USA* 97:7796–7801. DOI: 10.1073/pnas.97.14.7796.
- Szmyd R, Niska-Blakie J, Diril MK, Nunes PR, Tzelepis K, Lacroix A, van Hul N, Deng L-W, Matos J, Dreesen O, Bisteau X, Kaldis P 2019. Premature activation of Cdk1 leads to mitotic events in S phase and embryonic lethality. *Oncogene* 38:998–1018. DOI: 10.1038/s41388-018-0464-0.
- Sørensen CS, Syljuåsen RG, Falck J, Schroeder T, Rönnstrand L, Khanna KK, Zhou B-B, Bartek J, Lukas J 2003. Chk1 regulates the S phase checkpoint by coupling the physiological turnover and ionizing radiation-induced accelerated proteolysis of Cdc25A. *Cancer Cell* 3:247–258. DOI: 10.1016/S1535-6108(03)00048-5.
- Tachibana KEK, Gonzalez MA, Guarguaglini G, Nigg EA, Laskey RA 2005. Depletion of licensing inhibitor geminin causes centrosome overduplication and mitotic defects. *EMBO reports* 6:1052–1057. DOI: 10.1038/sj.embor.7400527.
- Takada M, Zhang W, Suzuki A, Kuroda TS, Yu Z, Inuzuka H, Gao D, Wan L, Zhuang M, Hu L, Zhai B, Fry CJ, Bloom K, Li G, Karpen GH, Wei W, Zhang Q 2017. FBW7 Loss Promotes Chromosomal Instability and Tumorigenesis via Cyclin E1/CDK2-Mediated Phosphorylation of CENP-A. *Cancer Res* 77:4881–4893. DOI: 10.1158/0008-5472.CAN-17-1240.
- Takahashi Y, Rayman JB, Dynlacht BD 2000. Analysis of promoter binding by the E2F and pRB families in vivo: distinct E2F proteins mediate activation and repression. *Genes & Development* 14:804–816.
- Takahashi-Yanaga F, Mori J, Matsuzaki E, Watanabe Y, Hirata M, Miwa Y, Morimoto S, Sasaguri T 2006. Involvement of GSK-3 β and DYRK1B in differentiation-inducing factor-3-induced phosphorylation of cyclin D1 in HeLa cells. *The Journal of biological chemistry* 281:38489–38497. DOI: 10.1074/jbc.M605205200.
- Takeda DY, Parvin JD, Dutta A 2005. Degradation of Cdt1 during S phase is Skp2-independent and is required for efficient progression of mammalian cells through S phase. *The Journal of biological chemistry* 280:23416–23423. DOI: 10.1074/jbc.M501208200.
- Tan Y, Sun D, Jiang W, Klotz-Noack K, Vashisht AA, Wohlschlegel J, Widschwendter M, Spruck C 2014. PP2A-B55 β antagonizes cyclin E1 proteolysis and promotes its dysregulation in cancer. *Cancer Res* 74:2006–2014. DOI: 10.1158/0008-5472.CAN-13-1263.
- Tanaka S, Araki H 2013. Helicase activation and establishment of replication forks at chromosomal origins of replication. *Cold Spring Harbor Perspectives in Biology* 5:a010371–a010371. DOI: 10.1101/cshperspect.a010371.
- Tanaka S, Komeda Y, Umemori T, Kubota Y, Takisawa H, Araki H 2013. Efficient initiation of DNA replication in eukaryotes requires Dpb11/TopBP1-GINS interaction. *Molecular and cellular biology* 33:2614–2622. DOI: 10.1128/MCB.00431-13.
- Tassan JP, Jaquenoud M, Fry AM, Frutiger S, Hughes GJ, Nigg EA 1995. In vitro assembly of a functional human CDK7-cyclin H complex requires MAT1, a novel 36 kDa RING finger protein. *The EMBO Journal* 14:5608–5617.
- Tatsumi Y, Ohta S, Kimura H, Tsurimoto T, Obuse C 2003. The ORC1 Cycle in Human Cells I. CELL CYCLE-REGULATED OSCILLATION OF HUMAN ORC1. *The Journal of biological chemistry* 278:41528–41534. DOI: 10.1074/jbc.M307534200.
- Thangavel S, Mendoza-Maldonado R, Tissino E, Sidorova JM, Yin J, Wang W, Monnat RJ, Falaschi A, Vindigni A 2010. Human RECQ1 and RECQ4 helicases play distinct roles in DNA replication initiation. *Molecular and cellular biology* 30:1382–1396. DOI: 10.1128/MCB.01290-09.
- Toledo LI, Altmeyer M, Rask M-B, Lukas C, Larsen DH, Povlsen LK, Bekker-Jensen S, Mailand N, Bartek J, Lukas J 2013. ATR Prohibits Replication Catastrophe by Preventing Global Exhaustion of RPA. *Cell* 155:1088–1103.
- UniProt Consortium 2019. UniProt: a worldwide hub of protein knowledge. *Nucleic Acids Res*. Jan 8;47(D1):D506-D515. doi: 10.1093/nar/gky1049.
- Vaites LP, Lee EK, Lian Z, Barbash O, Roy D, Wasik M, Klein-Szanto AJP, Rustgi AK, Diehl JA 2011. The Fbx4 tumor suppressor regulates cyclin D1 accumulation and prevents neoplastic transformation. *Molecular and cellular biology* 31:4513–4523. DOI: 10.1128/MCB.05733-11.
- Vandel L, Kouzarides T 1999. Residues phosphorylated by TFIIF are required for E2F-1 degradation during S-phase. *The EMBO Journal* 18:4280–4291. DOI: 10.1093/emboj/18.15.4280.
- Vigneron S, Sundermann L, Labbé JC, Pintard L, Radulescu O, Castro A, Lorca T 2018. Cyclin A-cdk1-Dependent Phosphorylation of Bora Is the Triggering Factor Promoting Mitotic Entry. *Developmental Cell* 45:637–650.e7. DOI: 10.1016/j.devcel.2018.05.005.
- Vos SM, Tretter EM, Schmidt BH, Berger JM 2011. All tangled up: how cells direct, manage and exploit topoisomerase function. *Nature reviews. Molecular cell biology* 12:827–841. DOI: 10.1038/nrm3228.
- Wang W-J, Acehan D, Kao C-H, Jane W-N, Uryu K, Tsou M-FB 2015. De novo centriole formation in human cells is error-prone and does not require SAS-6 self-assembly. *eLife* 4:1054. DOI: 10.7554/eLife.10586.
- Wardlaw CP, Carr AM, Oliver AW 2014. TopBP1: A BRCT-scaffold protein functioning in multiple cellular pathways. *DNA repair* 22:165–174. DOI: 10.1016/j.dnarep.2014.06.004.
- Watanabe N, Broome M, Hunter T 1995. Regulation of the human WEE1Hu CDK tyrosine 15-kinase during the cell cycle. *The EMBO Journal* 14:1878–1891.
- Wei Y, Jin J, Harper JW 2003. The cyclin E/Cdk2 substrate and Cajal body component p220(NPAT) activates histone transcription through a novel LisH-like domain. *Molecular and cellular biology* 23:3669–3680. DOI: 10.1128/mcb.23.10.3669-3680.2003.
- Welburn JPI, Tucker JA, Johnson T, Lindert L, Morgan M, Willis A, Noble MEM, Endicott JA 2007. How tyrosine 15 phosphorylation inhibits the activity of cyclin-dependent kinase 2-cyclin A. *The Journal of biological chemistry* 282:3173–3181. DOI: 10.1074/jbc.M609151200.
- Welcker M, Clurman BE 2008. FBW7 ubiquitin ligase: a tumour suppressor at the crossroads of cell division, growth and

- differentiation. *Nature reviews. Cancer* 8:83–93. DOI: 10.1038/nrc2290.
- Welcker M, Larimore EA, Swanger J, Bengoechea-Alonso MT, Grim JE, Ericsson J, Zheng N, Clurman BE 2013. Fbw7 dimerization determines the specificity and robustness of substrate degradation. *Genes & Development* 27:2531–2536.
- Welcker M, Singer J, Loeb KR, Grim J, Bloecher A, Gurien-West M, Clurman BE, Roberts JM 2003. Multisite Phosphorylation by Cdk2 and GSK3 Controls Cyclin E Degradation. *Molecular cell* 12:381–392. DOI: 10.1016/S1097-2765(03)00287-9.
- Werwein E, Cibis H, Hess D, Klempnauer K-H 2018. Activation of the oncogenic transcription factor B-Myb via multisite phosphorylation and prolyl cis/trans isomerization. *Nucleic acids research* 47:103–121.
- Westendorp B, Mokry M, Groot Koerkamp MJA, Holstege FCP, Cuppen E, de Bruin A 2012. E2F7 represses a network of oscillating cell cycle genes to control S-phase progression. *Nucleic acids research* 40:3511–3523.
- Wilsker D, Petermann E, Helleday T, Bunz F 2008. Essential function of Chk1 can be uncoupled from DNA damage checkpoint and replication control. *Proc Natl Acad Sci USA* 105:20752–20757. DOI: 10.1073/pnas.0806917106.
- Wohlschlegel JA, Dwyer BT, Dhar SK, Cvetic C, Walter JC, Dutta A 2000. Inhibition of eukaryotic DNA replication by geminin binding to Cdt1. *Science* 290:2309–2312. DOI: 10.1126/science.290.5500.2309.
- Won KA, Reed SI 1996. Activation of cyclin E/CDK2 is coupled to site-specific autophosphorylation and ubiquitin-dependent degradation of cyclin E. *The EMBO Journal* 15:4182–4193.
- Xu M, Sheppard KA, Peng CY, Yee AS, Piwnica-Worms H 1994. Cyclin A/CDK2 binds directly to E2F-1 and inhibits the DNA-binding activity of E2F-1/DP-1 by phosphorylation. *Molecular and cellular biology* 14:8420–8431. DOI: 10.1128/mcb.14.12.8420.
- Xu X, Huang S, Zhang B, Huang F, Chi W, Fu J, Wang G, Li S, Jiang Q, Zhang C 2017. DNA replication licensing factor Cdc6 and Plk4 kinase antagonistically regulate centrosome duplication via Sas-6. *Nat Commun* 8:15164. DOI: 10.1038/ncomms15164.
- Xu X, Rochette PJ, Feyissa EA, Su TV, Liu Y 2009. MCM10 mediates RECQ4 association with MCM2-7 helicase complex during DNA replication. *The EMBO Journal* 28:3005–3014. DOI: 10.1038/emboj.2009.235.
- Yang C-C, Suzuki M, Yamakawa S, Uno S, Ishii A, Yamazaki S, Fukatsu R, Fujisawa R, Sakimura K, Tsurimoto T, Masai H 2016. Claspin recruits Cdc7 kinase for initiation of DNA replication in human cells. *Nat Commun* 7:12135. DOI: 10.1038/ncomms12135.
- Ye X, Wei Y, Nalepa G, Harper JW 2003. The cyclin E/Cdk2 substrate p220(NPAT) is required for S-phase entry, histone gene expression, and Cajal body maintenance in human somatic cells. *Molecular and cellular biology* 23:8586–8600. DOI: 10.1128/mcb.23.23.8586-8600.2003.
- Yeeles JTP, Deegan TD, Janska A, Early A, Diffley JFX 2015. Regulated eukaryotic DNA replication origin firing with purified proteins. *Nature* 519:431–435. DOI: 10.1038/nature14285.
- Yeeles JTP, Janska A, Early A, Diffley JFX 2017. How the Eukaryotic Replisome Achieves Rapid and Efficient DNA Replication. *Molecular cell* 65:105–116. DOI: 10.1016/j.molcel.2016.11.017.
- Yim H, Park J-W, Woo SU, Kim S-T, Liu L, Lee C-H, Lee SK 2013. Phosphorylation of Cdc6 at serine 74, but not at serine 106, drives translocation of Cdc6 to the cytoplasm. *Journal of cellular physiology* 228:1221–1228. DOI: 10.1002/jcp.24275.
- Yu C, Gan H, Serra-Cardona A, Zhang L, Gan S, Sharma S, Johansson E, Chabes A, Xu R-M, Zhang Z 2018. A mechanism for preventing asymmetric histone segregation onto replicating DNA strands. *Science* 361:1386–1389. DOI: 10.1126/science.aat8849.
- Yuan R, Vos HR, van Es RM, Chen J, Burgering BM, Westendorp B, de Bruin A 2018. Chk1 and 14-3-3 proteins inhibit atypical E2Fs to prevent a permanent cell cycle arrest. *The EMBO Journal* 37:e97877. DOI: 10.15252/embj.201797877.
- Yuan Z, Riera A, Bai L, Sun J, Nandi S, Spanos C, Chen ZA, Barbon M, Rappsilber J, Stillman B, Speck C, Li H 2017. Structural basis of Mcm2–7 replicative helicase loading by ORC–Cdc6 and Cdt1. *Nature Structural & Molecular Biology* 24:316–324. DOI: 10.1038/nsmb.3372.
- Zaher MS, Rashid F, Song B, Joudeh LI, Sobhy MA, Tehseen M, Hingorani MM, Hamdan SM 2018. Missed cleavage opportunities by FEN1 lead to Okazaki fragment maturation via the long-flap pathway. *Nucleic acids research* 46:2956–2974.
- Zariwala M, Liu J, Xiong Y 1998. Cyclin E2, a novel human G1 cyclin and activating partner of CDK2 and CDK3, is induced by viral oncoproteins. *Oncogene* 17:2787–2798. DOI: 10.1038/sj.onc.1202505.
- Zegerman P 2013. DNA Replication: Polymerase Epsilon as a Non-catalytic Converter of the Helicase. *Current Biology* 23:R273–R276.
- Zhai Y, Cheng E, Wu H, Li N, Yung PYK, Gao N, Tye B-K 2017a. Open-ringed structure of the Cdt1–Mcm2–7 complex as a precursor of the MCM double hexamer. *Nature Structural & Molecular Biology* 24:300–308. DOI: 10.1038/nsmb.3374.
- Zhai Y, Li N, Jiang H, Huang X, Gao N, Tye B-K 2017b. Unique Roles of the Non-identical MCM Subunits in DNA Replication Licensing. *Molecular cell* 67:168–179.
- Zhao H, Piwnica-Worms H 2001. ATR-mediated checkpoint pathways regulate phosphorylation and activation of human Chk1. *Molecular and cellular biology* 21:4129–4139. DOI: 10.1128/MCB.21.13.4129-4139.2001.
- Zhao H, Watkins JL, Piwnica-Worms H 2002. Disruption of the checkpoint kinase 1/cell division cycle 25A pathway abrogates ionizing radiation-induced S and G2 checkpoints. *Proc Natl Acad Sci USA* 99:14795–14800. DOI: 10.1073/pnas.182557299.
- Zheng L, Shen B 2011. Okazaki fragment maturation: nucleases take centre stage. *Journal of molecular cell biology* 3:23–30.
- Zhou JC, Janska A, Goswami P, Renault L, Abid Ali F, Kotecha A, Diffley JFX, Costa A 2017. CMG-Pol epsilon dynamics suggests a mechanism for the establishment of leading-strand synthesis in the eukaryotic replisome. *Proc Natl Acad Sci USA* 114:4141–4146. DOI: 10.1073/pnas.1700530114.
- Ziebold U, Bartsch O, Marais R, Ferrari S, Klempnauer K-H 1997. Phosphorylation and activation of B-Myb by cyclin A–Cdk2. *Current Biology* 7:253–260. DOI: 10.1016/S0960-9822(06)00121-7.